

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Project Title	The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns
Project Acronym	VeriFish
Project Number	101156426
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Starting date of Project	01 May 2024
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.verifish.info

D3.6 – Communication, stakeholder engagement final report

Work Package	WP3 Communication outreach campaigns & prototype media products
Task	T3.1 Communication & Dissemination
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Version	V0.1
Due Date	30/04/2026
Submission Date	30/04/2026

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public, fully open
	SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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the European Union

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	24/04/2026	Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)	First draft before revisions
0.2	27/04/2026	Francesca Barazzeta (Eurofish)	Peer review revision
0.3	29/04/2026	Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)	Corrections to the first draft
0.4	30/04/2026	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT), Oda Bjørnsborg (Nofima)	Peer review revision
1.0	30/04/2026	Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)	Final draft

Keywords

VeriFish, communication and dissemination, stakeholder engagement, seafood sustainability, indicator framework, web application, factsheets, Community of Practice, educational media products, cookbook, social media outreach, newsletters, events, validation, Horizon Europe

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors like NOFIMA, EUROFIR and Poseidon. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

Glossary of terms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASC	Aquaculture Stewardship Council
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence
CEN	Comité Européen de Normalisation
CoP	Community of Practice
CTA	Call to Action
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DEM	Direct E-mail Marketing
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ETP	Endangered, Threatened and Protected
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FIP	Fishery Improvement Project
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PPC	Pay-Per-Click
QR	Quick Response
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SoMe	Social Media
STECF	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
T2	Tier 2
WP	Work Package
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature
Zenodo	Open-access research repository

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D3.6 Communication, stakeholder engagement final report is the final public report on communication, dissemination, campaigns, and stakeholder engagement under WP3 of VeriFish. Its purpose is to show how the project's technical results were translated into accessible formats, disseminated through different channels, and discussed with relevant stakeholders across the seafood value chain and beyond.

WP3 delivered a broad communication portfolio. The main outputs included the VeriFish website, the VeriFish web & mobile application and the browsable factsheets, twelve newsletters, seven Eurofish Magazine articles, twenty-three videos, social media campaigns, educational and awareness-raising media products, the cookbook and recipe cards, the Overfished! card game, the calendar, the fishing methods poster, the species puzzle, influencer campaigns, and a structured programme of internal and external events.

The project reached a wide range of stakeholder groups, including seafood producers, aquaculture actors, researchers, policy and advisory stakeholders, standards-related actors, educators, children and families, and the wider public. Engagement was strongest where stakeholders could interact directly with concrete outputs, especially the web-app, the factsheets, the educational materials, and the final event validation sessions. The Community of Practice reached 207 active communities and 100+ individuals, while direct requests (100+) for the web-app and media products showed clear external interest from organisations across research, education, industry, NGOs, and public institutions.

The most effective communication channels were the website and LinkedIn, supported by newsletters, videos, events, and targeted campaigns. The strongest formats were those that turned the VeriFish framework into practical tools and understandable content, especially the app, factsheets, educational products, and short videos. Overall, WP3 showed that the indicator framework can be communicated in accessible ways when the format matches the audience and when communication is linked to concrete outputs rather than abstract project messaging.

The main lesson is that communication worked best when it was built around tangible products, targeted formats, and opportunities for feedback or reuse. After the end of the project, several outputs retain clear value, particularly the website, the web-app, the factsheets, the cookbook, the educational materials, and the videos, which can continue to support awareness and understanding of responsible seafood communication beyond the project lifetime.

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2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose of the report

This report presents the results of the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities implemented under Work Package 3 of the VeriFish project. It provides an overview of the campaigns, channels, materials, and outreach actions developed during the 24-month (May 2024 - April 2026) implementation period to raise awareness of the project, promote its main assets, and support the dissemination of its results to the identified target groups. In doing so, it shows how VeriFish outputs were made more visible, accessible, and understandable for relevant audiences at local, national, and European level.

The report also documents the stakeholder engagement results achieved across the different categories addressed by the project, showing how stakeholders were informed, involved, and reached through the various activities carried out under WP3. In addition, it includes examples of how the VeriFish indicator framework was translated into different communication contexts, including digital tools, media products, educational materials, campaigns, and stakeholder-facing formats. The report explains how communication supported the practical understanding and uptake of verifiable seafood sustainability information across different user communities.

2.2. Position of D3.6 within WP3

Work Package 3 was dedicated to communication outreach campaigns and the development of prototype media products aimed at translating the project's technical results into formats that could be more easily accessed, understood, and used by different stakeholder groups. It played a central role in ensuring that the project's knowledge, tools, and messages were communicated through targeted dissemination actions, digital channels, educational and awareness-raising materials, stakeholder-oriented products, and public-facing activities. In this sense, WP3 acted as the link between the project's scientific and methodological work and its practical communication towards producers, consumers, policy actors, researchers, educators, and the wider public.

Deliverable D3.6 brings together the results of the communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and media product activities carried out during the project. It complements *D3.1 Communication, stakeholder engagement plan, including branding guide and promotional material*, which established the communication and dissemination roadmap, by reporting on how that strategy was implemented and what results were achieved. It also builds on *D3.2 VeriFish web app requirements & specification document* and *D3.3 VeriFish media products requirements & specification document*, which defined the specifications for the VeriFish web app and media products, by showing how those initial requirements informed later outputs. The report is also closely linked to *D3.7 Children & citizens media products* and *D3.8 VeriFish recipe book*, which focused on media products for children, younger generations, and citizens, as well as food and nutrition-oriented materials, since it assesses how these products contributed to outreach and uptake among different audiences. Finally, D3.6 complements *D3.9 VeriFish dissemination events roadmap* on the events and VeriFish conference roadmap by documenting

the dissemination and stakeholder engagement results associated with event participation and the final conference. Therefore, D3.6 serves as the final synthesis of WP3 implementation, connecting planning, product development, communication delivery, stakeholder interaction, and dissemination results in a single reporting framework.

2.3. Methodological note

The analysis presented in this report is based on evidence collected throughout the implementation of WP3 communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities. It draws on website analytics, social media metrics, newsletter records and performance indicators, published articles and editorial outputs, event participation records, Community of Practice activity, app-related outputs and demonstrations, campaign monitoring data, stakeholder feedback gathered through workshops and interactions, and contributions provided by the project partners involved in outreach and dissemination. Together, these sources make it possible to document both the scale of the activities carried out and their contribution to the visibility and communication of VeriFish results.

The report combines quantitative evidence with qualitative interpretation in order to provide a fuller account of WP3 implementation. Quantitative elements such as the number of materials produced, communication outputs published, event participations, social media reach, website visits, and newsletter performance are used to show the scale and distribution of activities across the project period. Qualitative interpretation is then used to assess the relevance of these activities, the nature of stakeholder responses, the usefulness of the products developed, and the extent to which different formats supported understanding and engagement with the VeriFish indicator framework. This combined approach is important because the performance of WP3 cannot be assessed only through visibility figures, but also through uptake, clarity, accessibility, and interaction with different audiences.

3. WP3 Overview: Objectives, audiences and implementation logic

3.1. Objectives of WP3

Work Package 3 was the communication and outreach work package of VeriFish. Its overall objective was to raise awareness of the project, inform relevant stakeholders, and promote its main assets among the identified target groups, while also increasing awareness of how to choose fish on the basis of verifiable indicators. This objective reflected a simple premise: the project's technical results would only have value beyond the consortium if they could be communicated in ways that were understandable, credible, and relevant to different users. WP3 was the part of the project where technical knowledge was translated into practical communication tools, campaigns, and media products with clear public and stakeholder-facing value.

A central aim of WP3 was to make complex sustainability-related information more usable without stripping it of substance. The VeriFish framework brought together environmental, socio-economic, nutritional, and related dimensions that are difficult to communicate clearly to non-specialist audiences.

WP3 addressed this by developing formats that could bridge the gap between technical results and practical understanding. This included digital tools, factsheets, videos, educational products, a recipe cookbook, and influencers' campaigns content designed for different user groups. The intention was to make information easier to access and interpret in real communication contexts.

Another key objective was to involve stakeholders in the development, testing, and refinement of outputs. WP3 combined outward communication with co-design, feedback collection, validation, and community-building. Through the Community of Practice, requirements gathering, workshops, continuous dialogue with the External Advisory Board (EAB) members, and events, the work package sought to ensure that VeriFish outputs were informed by the needs and perspectives of those expected to use, interpret, or circulate them. This was important for a project that aimed to influence how seafood sustainability information is communicated in practice.

More broadly, WP3 aimed to maximise the impact of project results through coordinated communication campaigns, synergies with relevant initiatives, online platforms, and stakeholder-oriented outreach activities. Its role was to create the conditions under which those materials could circulate, attract attention, and support informed engagement across different audiences. In that sense, WP3 combined a practical communication function with a broader strategic role in supporting the visibility, accessibility, and uptake of VeriFish results.

3.2. Stakeholder categories addressed

WP3 addressed a broad but structured set of stakeholder categories, reflecting the project's intention to operate across the seafood communication ecosystem. The main groups targeted were consumers and consumer associations, European citizens and families, children and younger generations, seafood retailers and HoReCa actors, fisheries associations, aquaculture producers, policy stakeholders and funding bodies, and standards-related or good-practice organisations. These categories mattered because VeriFish was designed as a communication approach intended to influence how seafood information is explained, understood, and potentially used across markets, institutions, education, and public awareness contexts.

Figure 1: Stakeholders identified by VeriFish project.

Consumers, citizens, and families were central to the awareness-raising dimension of WP3. They were primarily addressed through public-facing communication channels such as the website, social media, videos, storytelling content, and educational and practical media products. Children and younger generations were especially relevant for the development of simplified and engaging formats, including the card game, puzzle, calendar, poster, and cookbook, all of which provided more accessible entry points into seafood sustainability and nutrition themes.

Retailers, HoReCa actors, fisheries associations, and aquaculture producers were important because they operate at the interface between seafood production, market presentation, and consumer communication. These groups were relevant as potential future users of the framework, app, factsheets, and guidance-related outputs in real value-chain settings. They were engaged mainly through the app and factsheet logic, requirements gathering, the Community of Practice, and validation-oriented event participation.

Policy stakeholders, funding agencies, and standards-related actors were important for the institutional relevance and longer-term uptake of project results. Their value to VeriFish lay in their potential to influence how seafood communication might be structured, interpreted, or taken forward in more formal guidance or recommendation-oriented settings. They were reached mainly through more technical and

professional outputs, stakeholder events, the Community of Practice, and the wider dissemination environment created around the app, guidelines, and recommendation-linked work.

Combined, these categories show that WP3 was built around differentiated pathways through which different types of users could access, understand, test, or amplify VeriFish outputs depending on their role in the wider seafood communication landscape.

3.3. Partner roles in WP3

WP3 was led by Eurofish International Organisation and implemented through a multi-partner structure in which responsibilities were distributed across the different tasks according to expertise in communication, digital tools, stakeholder engagement, knowledge integration, and media product development. Eurofish had the overall leadership of the work package and played the central role in establishing the project's feedback community and broadcasting project results, working in collaboration with Trust-IT, its affiliated entity COMMpla, Nofima, EUROFIR, Poseidon, Clupea, Premotec and FORTH to develop the overall communication and outreach campaign and the prototype media products.

Overall, the distribution of roles in WP3 followed a coherent division of labour. Eurofish led the work package and the outward communication engine, Trust-IT anchored branding, co-design, and the Community of Practice by supporting the communication and stakeholder-facing logic in T3.1, COMMpla led the digital prototype and factsheet integration, EUROFIR led the broader media products task and food and nutrition outputs, FORTH supported the data and knowledge-based infrastructure behind the app and technical communication content, NOFIMA, Clupea and Poseidon contributed across the communication and media product tasks, and the wider project validation context, and the full consortium contributed to events and dissemination under T3.5. That structure mattered because WP3 required more than communication skills. It required communication, digital development, knowledge integration, stakeholder facilitation, educational translation, and sector credibility to work together in one coherent system.

4. Tasks 3.1 – Communication and Dissemination

4.1. Task objectives and implementation approach

Task 3.1 covered the project's communication and dissemination function throughout the full implementation period. In practical terms, the task was responsible for identifying relevant target audiences at local, national, and European level, defining clear key messages, selecting appropriate communication channels and campaign types, and maintaining a live editorial and dissemination approach that could evolve with the project itself. This made T3.1 the main coordinating task through which website content, social media activity, newsletters, editorial articles, audiovisual communication, and other dissemination materials could be planned and delivered in a coherent way.

The project addressed a diverse range of audiences, including citizens, consumers, producers, retailers, researchers, policy actors, educators, and other multiplier communities, each of whom required different levels of complexity, different narratives, and different entry points into the project's results. For that reason, the communication and editorial plan was treated as a live tool rather than a fixed document. This allowed messages, formats, and channels to be adjusted as the project developed and as new outputs became available. The approach combined broad communication about the project as a whole with more targeted dissemination of specific outputs, including the indicator framework, the guidelines, the web app, the factsheets, the media products, and related campaigns.

Communication under T3.1 was closely aligned with progress across the other work packages. This was particularly important in a project where dissemination depended on the gradual development of technical, methodological, and stakeholder-oriented outputs. As the project advanced its work on the indicator framework, scoring approaches, data integration, and guidance-related content, T3.1 translated those developments into more accessible narratives and dissemination materials suited to external audiences. As new tools and products were completed, including the web & mobile app, the factsheets, the videos, and the educational and awareness-raising products, the communication approach was updated to reflect their actual maturity. This ensured that communication remained credible, timely, and connected to the real progress of the project.

A further feature of T3.1 was the regular monitoring of digital platforms and communication activities. Website analytics, social media metrics, newsletter performance, influencers campaign data, and partner amplification were used to support the ongoing adjustment of actions during the project. This allowed communication to function as a dynamic process. Monitoring made it possible to observe which channels performed best, which types of content generated stronger attention or interaction, and how different audiences responded to specific outputs and campaigns. In this sense, the implementation of T3.1 combined planning with continuous adaptation, helping the project maintain communication that was both strategically coherent and responsive to stakeholder interest over time.

4.2. Target audiences, messages, and campaign logic

Communication choices were therefore shaped by the expected role of each stakeholder group, whether as future users of the framework and app, multipliers of project messages, contributors to validation and feedback, or recipients of educational and awareness-raising content.

Several key messages remained consistent across the project and gave coherence to the communication strategy.

- One central message was that seafood sustainability communication needs to be clearer, more transparent, and more evidence based.
- A second was that VeriFish was developing a framework based on verifiable indicators bringing together environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional dimensions in a more structured way.
- Communication also emphasised that VeriFish was translating this framework into practical outputs, including guidelines, factsheets, a web app, educational materials, and citizen-oriented media products.

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- A further recurring message was that complex sustainability information can be made more understandable without losing substance, and that better communication of verifiable information can support more informed choices across the seafood value chain.

These messages were adapted according to audience and format. For professional and institutional audiences, communication placed greater emphasis on methodological robustness, evidence-based communication, practical applicability, and the relevance of the project for guidance, implementation, and future uptake. For broader public-facing outputs, including social media content, educational materials, storytelling, and citizen-oriented campaigns, the messages were made more accessible, visual, and concrete, often focusing on understanding seafood better, making informed choices, and engaging with sustainability through everyday contexts. For outputs such as the web app and factsheets, communication highlighted usability and access to information, presenting VeriFish as a provider of practical tools. In this way, the campaign logic of T3.1 combined consistency of message with flexibility of format, tone, and level of depth depending on the audience and communication purpose.

4.3. Subtask 3.1.1 – Branding material

VeriFish developed a comprehensive Communication Kit available on the VeriFish website - Communication Kit section¹. It includes the VeriFish Brand Guidelines² to ensure a consistent and professional representation of the project across all platforms and communications. These guidelines defined the core elements of the project brand identity, including logos, colours, typography, and messaging, which helped convey VeriFish mission of promoting sustainable seafood practices through verifiable indicators. By adhering to these standards, the project ensured that all stakeholders, partners, and collaborators present a unified and recognizable image of VeriFish.

4.3.1. VeriFish Promotional materials

Throughout the project timeline, three distinct iterations of the **VeriFish flyer** were produced and distributed. Each version was strategically aligned with the project's progression to ensure stakeholders received the most current and relevant information:

- First Edition (May 2024-July 2024): Developed to introduce the fundamental aspects of the project. This version outlined the verifiable indicators, the tools being developed for consumers, and the project's overarching focus on responsible seafood production.
- Second Edition (June 2025): Published to coincide with the CEN Workshop Agreement Kick-Off event in Copenhagen. This iteration featured updated project initiatives and introduced a dedicated section detailing the Community of Practice (CoP) and the various pathways for stakeholder involvement.

¹ [Communication Kit section](#)

² [VeriFish Brand Guidelines](#)

- Third Edition (March 2026): Released in conjunction with the VeriFish final event in Brussels. This comprehensive final version detailed the VeriFish Indicator Framework Pillars and introduced the VeriFish web application. Furthermore, it integrated a QR code providing direct access to the project’s official deliverables hosted on the Zenodo repository.

One roll-up was also designed and brought at all key event of the project.

In addition to banners, campaign visuals, and event-related communication materials, VeriFish also developed **branded business cards** as part of its dissemination toolkit. These were used primarily during conferences, fairs, stakeholder meetings, and networking activities to support direct contact with external audiences and provide a simple offline entry point to the project. The business cards contributed to the professional presentation of the project and helped reinforce a consistent visual identity during in-person dissemination activities.

Figure 2: VeriFish Flyers first edition (July 2024) - Front

The importance of Sustainable Seafood

In today's world, sustainable seafood is more critical than ever. Sustainable practices ensure that we can enjoy the health benefits of these foods while preserving the environment for future generations. By choosing sustainably sourced seafood, we support responsible industry practices that help maintain fish populations, protect marine habitats, and reduce the environmental impact of our consumption.

What do we mean when talking about sustainable seafood?

Sustainability and nutrient values

Citizens need trustworthy information on sustainability and nutrition. While seafood is a good source of high-quality protein and nutrients, its sustainability varies. Understanding these differences empowers consumers to make healthier and environmentally responsible choices. VeriFish provides a framework with verifiable indicators to help identify sustainable seafood options.

Provenance

Understanding the origin of seafood is essential for assessing sustainability. Locally sourced seafood typically has a lower carbon footprint and benefits local economies. However, poor labelling can lead consumers to unknowingly select products that harm overfishing and ecosystems. VeriFish addresses this issue by providing clear information about origin.

Potential health risk and benefits

Seafood has many health benefits but can also pose risks due to contaminants like mercury, microplastics, and harmful bacteria. VeriFish aims to provide more transparent information about the safety and health benefits of seafood, enabling consumers to make informed choices and enjoy seafood confidently.

VeriFish Indicator Framework: Enhancing Environmental Sustainability in Fisheries

VeriFish will enable integration of indicators from various sources and provide recommendations for seafood businesses on how to present information about different products for consumer groups.

The VeriFish framework enables scoring information from different sources based on reliability and presents key information about seafood products in a standardised manner. Aspects include definitions, methods, sources, and indicators for sustainability, origin, and health sourced from organisations like the FAO, EuroFIR, and FISHBASE to ensure validity.

Fisheries and Aquaculture

VeriFish Indicator framework addresses both captured fishery and aquaculture. Fisheries are essential for sustainable seafood but good management practices are key to maintaining fish populations and preventing resource depletion. Challenges like overfishing, bycatch, and habitat destruction need to be addressed to help protect ocean health and ensure fish stocks remain viable. Aquaculture, or fish farming, can help meet growing demand for seafood and ease pressure on wild fish stocks provided they are managed sustainably. However, aquaculture faces challenges like habitat degradation, water pollution, and disease. Sustainable practices, and tools like VeriFish, are crucial for ensuring farmed seafood remains environmentally friendly and safe, simplifying the complex landscape of seafood consumption.

VeriFish Web application

By converting the VeriFish Indicator framework into an easy-to-navigate format, the VeriFish web app will provide comprehensive information to guide users towards informed choices. It will describe the status of stocks, biological characteristics of species, environmental data, and nutrient content as well as how these relate to health benefits. The entry point of the web app will be a QR code, allowing users to access detailed product information, including labels, indicators, descriptions, and links to resources.

Guidelines and visuals

To facilitate understanding and use of indicators, users will be able to view them as a spider/radar chart that supports connections among desires and possible solutions that are otherwise difficult to understand. It will allow users to integrate local, seasonal, or health concerns with wider sectoral environmental impact mitigation plans, sustainability of the fisheries, and EU-wide nutritional data.

VeriFish will also deliver comprehensive guidelines on how to use indicators to help retailers and producers communicate the sustainability of their products.

Towards a standardised approach to sustainable seafood communication

One of the key deliverables of VeriFish is a European good practice recommendation, providing a standardised approach for communicating about sustainable seafood.

- 👤 For citizens, it will provide clear and trustworthy information to help make informed choices.
- 👤 For retailers and producers, it will offer a standardised method for showcasing sustainability of their products, helping build consumer trust and loyalty.
- 👤 For policymakers, it will help with design, implementation, and review of regulations and initiatives.

Figure 3: VeriFish Flyers first edition (July 2024) - Back

Figure 4: VeriFish Roll-up Banner

Figure 5: VeriFish Business cards.

4.3.2. VeriFish digital visual materials

Throughout the project, a broad range of visual materials were developed to support communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and the promotion of specific outputs and events. These materials included banners and SoMe campaign visuals prepared for the project website, newsletters, social media, partner communication, and event-related dissemination, as well as the dedicated assets created for public-facing initiatives such as the VeriFish Photo Challenge. Taken together, these materials formed an important part of the project’s visual communication infrastructure, helping to ensure consistency of identity, strengthen recognisability across channels, and made project messages more accessible and appealing to different audiences.

A significant part of this work involved the preparation of banners and graphic materials linked to key project moments and outputs. These included visuals developed for the project kick-off meeting, the final event, newsletter promotion, as well as materials prepared for pay-per-click and other targeted communication actions. They served practical communication purposes by framing announcements,

supporting event visibility, increasing the clarity of calls to action, and reinforcing the connection between individual communication pieces and the wider VeriFish identity. In the case of newsletters and event promotion, banners provided continuity across communication formats, while for digital campaigns they offered a more direct and visually recognisable route into project content.

Within this broader visual communication effort, the VeriFish Photo Challenge represented a participatory and outward-facing campaign initiative. Running from February to May 2025, the challenge invited participants from across Europe to submit photographs and captions that captured their own interpretation of sustainable seafood. The objective was to connect people with the environmental, nutritional, and socio-economic dimensions of fisheries and aquaculture through visual storytelling and to encourage a more personal and reflective form of engagement with the themes of the project.

The Photo Challenge received more than 15 entries from students, seafood professionals, and citizens interested in the future of oceans and sustainable seafood systems. Each submission reflected a distinct perspective on seafood, sustainability, and community, and together they helped broaden the communicative tone of the project by introducing a more participatory and human-centred element into the dissemination strategy. In this sense, the challenge complemented the more formal outputs of the project by making the wider purpose of VeriFish more relatable and by inviting users to contribute rather than only observe.

The visuals presented below therefore include not only the specific materials developed for the VeriFish Photo Challenge, but also the wider set of banners and campaign graphics created across the project for newsletters, project meetings, the final event, targeted campaigns, and other dissemination actions. Together, they illustrate how visual identity and graphic communication were used to support the visibility, coherence, and public accessibility of VeriFish throughout its implementation.

Figure 6: Photo Challenge Promotional Banner

Figure 7: Example of Newsletter promotional banner

Figure 8: CWA Kick Off Promotional Banner

Figure 9: VeriFish Final Event Banner

Figure 10: Example of PPC Banner Campaign - "Why Seafood Matters: Biology".

EPO2_175

VeriFish

www.verifish.info

Funded by the European Union

1. Indicator Framework: Rationale & Objectives

Need to simplify and standardise communication to consumers by those in the food chain to help increase consumption of sustainable seafood.

- No verified indicators to inform consumers about sustainability, nutrients and health, or climate impacts of seafood.
- Complexity of the food chains make it challenging for actors to present accurate and understandable information, limiting consumer choice.

Re-use of VeriFish Framework will help ensure:

- Consumers can trust nutritional quality of seafood
- Impacts on food security and the environment are minimised
- Use of natural resources does not exceed what is sustainable

2. Attributes & Indicators

Attribute: Characteristic that provides information or helps understanding e.g., Atlantic salmon or Salmo salar

Indicator: Measurable variable, e.g., stock status of a species caught in a particular region with a specific type of gear

3. Types of data source

TIER 1 data: Publicly available sources, such as FAO online databases

Advantages: Usually free of cost and is generally well-validated

Weaknesses: Not available for all indicators, high level

TIER 2 data: Provided by value chain, specifically relating to production methods, products and processes

Advantages: Relatively high degree of detail and

Disadvantages: Potentially subject to bias or error; independent verification and collection required

Framework includes 84 indicators, mapped to over 35 data sources

4. Technical Implementation

USING THE VERIFISH FRAMEWORK

a. Nutrient quality scoring

To support informed consumption, a nutrient density score can be applied to seafood, ranking products by contribution to human health, based on EFSA nutrient reference values (Jhalilabadi et al., 2018).

NDS is calculated per 100g of uncooked seafood using:

- 25 qualitative nutrients (e.g. omega-3, protein, vitamins, minerals)
- 2 disqualifying nutrients (sodium, saturated fat)

Ranking Categories: Very good: >13 | Good: 6-13 | Acceptable: <6

- Enables comparison across seafood and meats
- Transparent and standardised scoring

EuroFIR
European Food Information Resource

b. VeriFish game - "Overfished"

c. VeriFish Mobile App

VeriFish Framework: Pillars ■ Indicators & Data Sources

Nutrition & Health	Socioeconomic	Environmental
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nutrient density scoring Transparency indicators (sodium, saturated fat) Reference to FAO and adapted indicators (e.g. CO2e) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Labour rights (e.g. SD, slavery rating) Government and transparency (e.g. traceability) Working conditions and fair wages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stock status (e.g. MSC, ISEAL) Ecosystem impact (bycatch, habitat) Climate impact (CO2e measured) Catchability and effort
<p>FAO/WHO/UNEP, Food Systems, FoodNet, World Health Organization, Global Nutrition Report</p>	<p>FAO, World Bank, ILO, OECD, UN Women, Transparency International, Sustainable Development Goals, Fisheries activities (DEED), WFP, Port State Measures, ILO Conventions, ILO Global Agri Index, Global Slavery Index, Trafficking in Persons</p>	<p>Apparel: ERM, Eco-Fish, ASC, EU MSC, EMU/Net, Biorisk, Capture Fisheries, Fishbase, Seafood Carbon Footprint Tool, EMU/Net, Seaaround, IOD, ERM, BMS, NOK, ERM, OFEL, OAS, WFP (WFP 2018), Eco-Fish, SDG 14/15 Marine, 14/15-visual-Kit, Fish4Impact</p>

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquaculture production and consumption patterns (VeriFish) received funding under Topic: W09294855-2023-OCEAN-01-10 (Project no. 101196426).

VeriFish is a project of the European Union. The content of this document does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union or the Commission. The Commission is not responsible for any use of the information contained herein.

Figure 11: VeriFish Poster released for the 23rd International Congress of Nutrition (ICN 2025) in Paris, France August 2025 attended by EuroFIR.

Figure 12: Example of infographics designed for the VeriFish Knowledge Base Data Sources

Figure 13: VeriFish artwork at the Eurofish Stand in Aquaculture Europe 2025 (September 2025, Valencia, Spain)

Figure 14: Wall Art Aquaculture Europe 2025 in Valencia

Figure 15: Counter Art Aquaculture Europe 2025 in Valencia

Figure 16: Badges for VeriFish events.

4.4. Subtask 3.1.2 VeriFish public website & social media outreach (Eurofish)

4.4.1. VeriFish Website

The VeriFish public website (<https://verifish.info/>) was launched in September 2024 and maintained as the project's main public-facing communication channel and served as the central hub through which external audiences could access information on the project's objectives, consortium, work structure, outputs, and dissemination materials. As the project progressed, the website evolved from a general presentation space into a more results-oriented platform containing dedicated sections on the project sustainability pillars (https://verifish.info/Indicators/#Sustainability_Pillars), the indicator framework (<https://verifish.info/indicators/>), the web app (<https://verifish.info/verifish-web-app/>), produced media products (<https://verifish.info/verifish-media-product/>), including the VeriFish cookbook (<https://verifish.info/verifish-cookbook/>), the CEN Workshop Agreement (<https://verifish.info/verifish-media-product/>), campaign materials, and other public resources. This progressive expansion was important because it allowed the website to reflect the actual maturity and in practice, it became the main destination for audiences arriving from direct access, search engines, social media, referrals, email-based traffic, and event-related communication, while also functioning as the reference point for stakeholders looking for more detailed and structured information than could be conveyed through shorter communication formats.

Figure 17: VeriFish website frontpage (<https://verifish.info/>) Date: 14/04/2026.

Website performance shows that the site played a meaningful role in the visibility and dissemination of VeriFish. During the period from August 2025 to April 2026³, the website recorded 4,994 total users, of whom 4,984 were new users, generating 7,290 sessions. The analytics also show 10,290 page views, 7,275 session starts, 5,651 user engagement events, and 4,984 first visits, confirming that the site attracted repeated interaction beyond simple access. Scroll activity was recorded 2,175 times, while click events reached 461, suggesting that users did not only land on the site but also navigated and interacted with elements on it. Additional interactions included 419 form starts, 62 form submissions, 107 video starts, and 306 video progress events, which indicates a more active use of site content than a superficial visit pattern would suggest.

Figure 18: VeriFish website performance over time (Active Users and New Users) on the period between August 2025 and April 2026 (Date: 14/04/2026)

Website traffic was driven mainly by direct access, which generated 4,403 sessions, followed by organic search with 1,624 sessions, organic social with 910 sessions, referral traffic with 300 sessions, and a smaller unassigned segment with 40 sessions. This shows that the website benefited both from users intentionally accessing it and from visibility created through search, social media, and external references.

The homepage remained the main entry point, but several internal pages also generated substantial sessions, showing that communication efforts directed users towards specific outputs and event-related content. In particular, the final event, cookbook, web app, media products, card game, and CEN Workshop

³ A methodological clarification is necessary in relation to the website analytics presented in this report. Comparable quantitative website data were available only for the period from August 2025 to April 2026, and website activity prior to August 2025 is therefore not included in the quantitative analysis. This limitation should be considered in light of the fact that the volume, diversity, and maturity of website content increased significantly from August 2025 onwards, as more project outputs, public-facing resources, and dedicated content sections became available. As a result, the traffic patterns observed during the analysed period are not necessarily representative of the earlier phase of the project, when the website contained a lighter set of materials and served a more introductory function

Agreement pages all attracted targeted traffic, indicating that dissemination was not limited to general website visibility.

Overall, the website combined broad visibility with direct access to concrete resources. The traffic pattern suggests that VeriFish communication was effective not only in bringing users to the site, but also in guiding them towards specific outputs linked to their interests.

4.4.2. Social Media (SoMe)

Social media outreach complemented the website by creating repeated, audience-specific entry points into the project. Across its social media channels, VeriFish reached a combined total of 1.146 followers by the reporting point (30/04/2026). Although the size of the audience remained uneven across platforms, the combined presence shows that VeriFish succeeded in establishing a recognisable digital footprint around complex topics that does not naturally lend itself to mass social media engagement. The overall impact of VeriFish communication was strongest where social media activity was connected to tangible assets and credible dissemination moments, demonstrating that the project was able to convert a relatively specialised subject into a visible and usable public communication effort.

The project maintained a presence on LinkedIn, Instagram, X, Facebook, and, at a later stage, Bluesky. By the reporting point, the LinkedIn page had reached 916 followers, making it the strongest platform in terms of audience size and professional relevance. Instagram counted 134 followers, X 44 followers, Facebook 30 followers, and Bluesky 22 followers. These figures reflect a communication ecosystem in which the project's strongest traction was clearly concentrated on LinkedIn, while the other platforms played a more complementary role in supporting visual communication, awareness-raising, or broader visibility. This outcome is consistent with the nature of the project, since VeriFish combined scientific, methodological, policy-relevant, and stakeholder-oriented outputs that were especially well suited to professional and institutional audiences active on LinkedIn.

4.4.2.1. LinkedIn

LinkedIn was the most strategically relevant social media channel used by VeriFish during the project, reaching 916 followers and consolidating itself as the main platform for communication with professional, institutional, scientific, and sector-oriented audiences. The project made between 2-3 publications per week normally, with more during events. Its role within the communication strategy was not limited to simple visibility, but extended to the structured dissemination of project results, milestone announcements, public invitations, event-related communication, and the promotion of concrete outputs such as the web app, the cookbook, the newsletter, and other public-facing resources. The platform was particularly well suited to the nature of VeriFish because it allowed the project to position itself within discussions related to fisheries, aquaculture, seafood sustainability, food systems, policy, and EU-funded innovation. The channel worked most effectively when the project offered something specific to explore, download, discuss, or attend, making LinkedIn not only the largest platform in audience terms, but also the most aligned with the project's core dissemination objectives. This is particularly visible in the stronger performance of result-based and externally anchored posts on LinkedIn, where content connected to real products, deadlines, public invitations, or visible project milestones appears to have attracted more attention than purely institutional communication.

Figure 19: VeriFish LinkedIn Page banner (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/verifishproject/>) Date: 29/04/2026.

4.4.2.2. Instagram

Instagram played a more modest but still useful role within the social media ecosystem of the project, reaching 134 followers and supporting the visual and more accessible side of VeriFish communication. While its audience size remained significantly smaller than that of LinkedIn, the platform offered value in presenting the project in a more immediate and recognisable format, particularly through visual posts, campaign graphics, short videos, awareness materials, and content linked to products and storytelling. Instagram was better suited to lighter, more accessible communication than to highly technical or policy-oriented content and therefore functioned mainly as a complementary channel rather than as a primary vehicle for result-driven dissemination. Its usefulness lay in helping the project translate more complex themes into formats that could reach broader or more visually oriented audiences, especially where the goal was not detailed explanation, but initial attention, familiarity, or public-facing awareness.

Figure 20: VeriFish Instagram Profile (https://www.instagram.com/verifish_project/) Date: 13/04/2026.

4.4.2.3. X/Twitter

X was kept as a supporting dissemination channel and reached 44 followers by the reporting point. Its main value lay in the rapid circulation of short updates, event-linked visibility, and connections with broader project, research, and thematic ecosystems where concise and timely communication is common. For VeriFish, X was not the principal platform for deep engagement or sustained audience growth, but rather a channel that could support the amplification of milestones, promote participation in events or public processes, and increase the visibility of announcements already anchored in other communication channels. As with many research and innovation projects, its effectiveness depended heavily on timing, relevance, and the wider ecosystem of accounts engaging with the same topic. In that sense, X functioned more as an auxiliary visibility tool than as a core dissemination asset, and its smaller audience size reflects that role.

Figure 21: VeriFish X profile (https://x.com/Verifish_project) Date: 13/04/2026

4.4.2.4. Facebook

Facebook was used as a complementary public-facing channel and reached 30 followers during the project. Its contribution to the overall communication strategy was more limited than LinkedIn and more generalist in character, supporting the circulation of awareness-oriented posts, visual content, selected project outputs, and campaign materials in a format accessible to broader audiences. The platform offered some value for maintaining an additional public presence and for extending the project's communication beyond purely professional networks, but it did not appear to function as a major driver of traffic, stakeholder interaction, or high-value engagement. For a project such as VeriFish, whose outputs required a certain degree of contextual explanation and whose strongest audiences were often professional or institutional, Facebook was useful mainly as a secondary dissemination space rather than as a leading channel.

Figure 22: VeriFish Facebook profile (<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61558684007435>) Date: 13/04/2026

4.4.2.5. Bluesky

Bluesky was incorporated as an additional and emerging social media space and reached 22 followers. Its role in the project was clearly complementary and exploratory, rather than central. It provided a small but potentially relevant outlet for sharing short updates, links to public outputs, and selected pieces of project communication within an evolving social media environment. Given its limited audience size and the late-stage or secondary nature of its use, Bluesky did not play a decisive role in the project's communication results. However, its inclusion reflects an effort to diversify the project's public visibility and maintain some adaptability in the choice of social channels. In practical terms, it functioned as a low-volume extension of the broader dissemination effort rather than as a channel with significant standalone impact.

Figure 23: VeriFish Bluesky profile (<https://bsky.app/profile/verifish.bsky.social>) Date: 13/04/2024

4.4.2.6. Social Media Analysis

Social media strategy included result-focused posts presenting concrete deliverables and assets such as the guidelines, app, factsheets, cookbook, and educational products; event-oriented communication related to conferences, working groups, fairs, clustering workshops, and project meetings; awareness-raising content built around the wider relevance of seafood sustainability communication; and storytelling or explanatory content aimed at making the project's objectives and tools more accessible to non-specialist audiences. In addition, fish- and seafood-related thematic communication helped connect the abstract concept of verifiable indicators to more tangible and recognisable contexts. This variety of campaign types was necessary because VeriFish was promoting a broader framework, a set of tools, and a communication approach that needed to be translated differently depending on the stage of the project and the intended audience.

Social media approach also required continuous testing and adjustment across channels, since performance could not be assumed in advance. For this reason, different platforms, including smaller or emerging ones such as Bluesky, were also used to assess their potential for reaching relevant audiences. The results showed that some channels generated more limited traction, while LinkedIn consistently produced stronger reach and interaction. This allowed the project to adapt its effort over time and concentrate more strongly on the platforms that proved most effective, meaning that lower figures on some channels should be understood not simply as weak performance, but as part of a necessary process of testing, learning, and optimisation.

Table 1: Overview of the main communication channels used under Subtask 3.1.2, including their role within the project communication strategy, primary audience profile, audience size or traffic, and the main types of content disseminated through each channel.

Channel	Main role in project communication	Main audience profile	Audience size / users reached	Main content types
Project website (verifish.info)	Main public-facing information hub and central destination for project results, resources, and updates	All external audiences, including stakeholders seeking structured information on the project, its outputs, and public materials	4,990 total users, 4,986 new users, 7,331 sessions during the reporting period	Project overview, partner information, work package outputs, indicator framework content, web app pages, cookbook, educational materials, campaign resources, news and updates
LinkedIn	Main professional dissemination channel and strongest platform for project visibility among sectoral and institutional audiences	Researchers, policy actors, seafood sector stakeholders, partner organisations, EU project communities, professional multipliers	916 followers	Deliverable and result-focused posts, event promotion, milestones, public invitations, app-related communication, guidelines, factsheets, videos, stakeholder-oriented updates
Instagram	Visual awareness-raising channel supporting more accessible and public-facing communication	General public, younger audiences, visually oriented followers, awareness-focused users	134 followers	Visual campaign posts, storytelling content, videos, awareness materials, educational and public-interest content
X	Fast-update channel supporting short-form dissemination, visibility during events, and topical communication	Project ecosystem followers, thematic communities, event audiences, research and innovation networks	44 followers	Short updates, event communication, milestone announcements, links to project news, dissemination of public outputs
Facebook	Support channel for broader visibility and more general-audience dissemination	Citizens, general public, community-oriented audiences, followers of project pages and shared content	30 followers	Awareness posts, visual materials, campaign promotion, public-facing updates, selected project outputs
Bluesky	Complementary channel for light dissemination and visibility in emerging social media spaces	Small general and thematic audience, early adopters, followers of alternative social platforms	22 followers	Short updates, project news, links to public outputs, complementary awareness content

4.5. Subtask 3.1.3 Newsletter & DEM

The VeriFish newsletter⁴ was a recurring dissemination tool designed to maintain continuity of communication with stakeholders beyond the shorter and faster logic of social media. The newsletter was conceived as a more stable and structured communication format through which the project could

⁴ <https://verifish.info/newsletters/>

provide consolidated updates, highlight relevant outputs, and keep interested audiences connected to project developments over time. In line with the original planning, the newsletter was implemented as a regular communication product with an expected bi-monthly rhythm. VeriFish published its first newsletter in October 2024 and, by 13 April 2026, had produced a total of 12 newsletters. The initial publication rhythm followed a two-month cycle until January 2026, after which the frequency increased to monthly publication as the project approached its final phase and a greater number of results, events, and public-facing outputs became available for dissemination. At the time of this review, an additional final newsletter had also been prepared in order to summarise the project and communicate its closing stage and key achievements.

The newsletter targeted an audience already interested in the project and willing to receive more sustained and structured information than would usually be delivered through social media. By the reporting point, the subscriber base stood at 84 subscribers. For a project such as VeriFish, which addressed a technically specialised theme and developed outputs of direct interest mainly to engaged stakeholders, the newsletter functioned as a channel for stakeholder retention, continuity, and repeated contact. In this sense, its value lay less in scale and more in the fact that it allowed the project to maintain an in-depth and cumulative relationship with readers already interested in seafood sustainability communication, project results, events, and public resources.

Across the reporting period, the newsletter followed a stable structure that helped maintain recognisability and coherence. Each issue typically combined project news, events attended and upcoming, media products, the CEN Workshop Agreement process, Community of Practice updates, and a final call to action. This made the newsletter a useful synthesis tool, allowing VeriFish to present several developments in one place and helping readers follow the project over time.

The newsletter reflected the broad communication scope of WP3 while giving space to recurring themes such as educational content, recipes, nutritional information, stakeholder opportunities, media product releases, and progress towards the final events. Because it offered more space than social media, it allowed outputs to be framed in context rather than as isolated announcements.

Its role was therefore different from that of social media. While social channels were stronger for immediate visibility, the newsletter supported continuity and retention by keeping an already interested audience informed and connected throughout the project. It worked less as a high-volume visibility channel and more as a relationship-building tool for stakeholders with a sustained interest in VeriFish results.

4.6. Subtask 3.1.4 Eurofish Magazine articles (Eurofish)

Subtask 3.1.4 included the publication of VeriFish-related articles in Eurofish Magazine as part of the project's dissemination strategy towards professional audiences and market-oriented stakeholders. This channel was particularly relevant because Eurofish Magazine already reaches 2300 monthly/bimonthly readers with a direct interest in fisheries, aquaculture, seafood markets, value chains, policy developments, and sector innovation. The articles published under this subtask therefore provided the project with a communication format that was more durable and contextualised than social media, while

also being more accessible and audience-oriented than formal technical deliverables. Through these contributions, VeriFish was able to communicate its objectives, progress, campaigns, and selected results in a format well suited to readers who are familiar with sector dynamics and interested in applied developments relevant to seafood sustainability and communication.

The published articles covered a range of themes across the life of the project.

- 2025: Issue 6 (December): Seafood Sustainability is not a joke:
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/em6_25/51
- 2025: Issue 5 (October): Catch Welfare Conference and VeriFish working lunch
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/em5-2025_september_lr/15
- 2025: Issue 4 (August): VeriFish Photo Challenge
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/eurofish_magazine_4_2025/26
- 2025: Issue 4 (August): Latest milestones from VeriFish
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/eurofish_magazine_4_2025/25
- 2025: Issue 2 (April): VeriFish Indicator Framework
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/eurofish_magazine_2_2025/21
- 2024: Issue 4 (August): VeriFish introduction
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/eurofish_magazine_4_2025/33
- 2024: Issue 3 (June): VeriFish Kick off Meeting press release
https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/eurofish_magazine_3_2024/7

Together, these articles addressed different communication needs, ranging from project introduction and launch visibility to explanation of the framework itself, dissemination of milestones, engagement-oriented campaign coverage, and participation in thematic events linked to the wider seafood sustainability debate. In addition, an article reviewing the project as a whole and its major outcomes is planned for publication in Eurofish Magazine Issue 3 of 2026, which will further strengthen the closing communication of the project.

Figure 24: First page of the VeriFish article published on the Eurofish Magazine in April 2025 (EFM2/25)

In terms of delivery against target, the results exceeded expectations. The communication planning foresaw the publication of at least five Eurofish Magazine articles during the project, and by the reporting point seven articles had already been published. This means that the target was not only met but surpassed, providing the project with a stronger editorial footprint than originally required. This is significant because it shows that Eurofish Magazine was not used merely as a symbolic dissemination channel, but as an active and recurring component of the project's communication work. The range of themes covered also suggests that the magazine articles were used strategically across different phases of the project.

These articles contributed particularly well to communication towards professional audiences and market actors because they framed VeriFish within the language and concerns of the seafood sector. The magazine format allowed the project to explain concepts, connect project developments to wider sector debates, and situate outputs within practical and policy-relevant contexts. For professional readers, this is critical. The articles helped position VeriFish not only as a Horizon Europe project, but as a relevant initiative within the professional conversation on seafood sustainability, transparency, communication, and stakeholder engagement.

4.7. Subtask 3.1.5 VeriFish trailer series

The VeriFish trailer and short video series serves as a core pillar of the project’s digital communication strategy. Its primary narrative role is to translate the multidimensional complexities of seafood sustainability, spanning environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional aspects, into accessible and engaging visual content. By strategically breaking down intricate data points, scientific concepts, and policy-related issues into shorter and more human-centred narratives, the series was designed to reach audiences beyond the scientific community and to support responsible decision-making regarding nutrition, biodiversity, and sustainability. In this sense, the video series did not merely promote the project. It helped explain how individual indicators, when considered together, contribute to a more comprehensive sustainability profile for the future of aquafood.

By combining expert interviews, short explainers, event-based recordings, and storytelling-oriented pieces, the series allowed VeriFish to communicate complexity in a more direct and legible format than written deliverables alone could offer. This was especially important for a project dealing with several interconnected pillars and multiple layers of evidence. The videos helped make the project more understandable by showing how sustainability can be discussed not only through data and frameworks, but also through the voices of researchers, practitioners, market actors, and fishers. As a result, the trailer and video series played both an explanatory and a narrative role within the overall communication strategy.

4.7.1. Video Production, Channels, and Promotion Approach

To date (29/04/2026), a total of 28 videos have been successfully produced and published on the VeriFish YouTube channels. Content was primarily captured during official consortium meetings, project events, and dissemination activities where the physical presence of key experts, stakeholders, and collaborators could be used efficiently for audiovisual production. This was a pragmatic approach that allowed the project to produce a relatively diverse body of video content without depending on standalone filming exercises detached from the project’s operational calendar.

The official VeriFish YouTube channel⁵ served as the primary repository for the audiovisual content, from which the videos were further distributed through the project’s main social media platforms and featured through the project website⁶ and related campaigns. This model was particularly useful because it allowed a single piece of video content to function across several layers of communication at once: as a stand-alone output on YouTube, as shorter promotional content through LinkedIn and other channels, and as supporting material for newsletters, event communication, or public-facing website pages.

The YouTube analytics confirm that the video output generated measurable interest. Across the channel, the published video content accumulated 663 views, 8.9 hours of watch time, 22 subscribers gained, and 5100 impressions.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@Verifish/videos>

⁶ <https://verifish.info/interactive-seafood-insights/#Videos>

4.7.2. Thematic Video Series Produced

4.7.2.1. 2 Questions, 6 Perspectives⁷

This communication campaign highlighted diverse expert insights through a common interview format. Experts from the consortium responded to two fundamental questions:

1. Why is sustainability in fisheries and aquaculture important today?
2. How does VeriFish contribute to raising awareness about sustainable seafood?

The format gave coherence to the campaign while allowing each expert to bring a different perspective. Featured experts included:

- [Christine Absil \(Clupea\)](#)
- [Michelle Boonstra \(Clupea\)](#)
- [Ixai Salvo \(Eurofish\)](#)
- [Tim Huntington \(Poseidon\)](#)
- [Siân Astley \(EuroFIR\)](#)
- [Themistoklis Altintzoglou \(NOFIMA\)](#)

Figure 25: Preview Playlist “2 Questions, 6 Perspectives” on VeriFish YouTube Channel

In performance terms, the series generated a modest but useful level of visibility. Among the videos, Michelle Boonstra’s entry reached 31 views, Ixai Salvo’s 17, Themistoklis Altintzoglou’s 14, Christine Absil’s 10, Tim Huntington’s 7, Siân Astley’s 5, and.

⁷ https://verifish.info/interactive-seafood-insights/#Two_questions_six_perspectives

4.7.2.2. *Building the VeriFish Knowledge Base: Why Reliable Fisheries Data Matters*⁸

This in-depth interview with Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)⁹ explained the architecture of the project's knowledge base and emphasised how VeriFish aggregates verified environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional data to support transparency and more informed decision-making.

The video played an important explanatory role because it addressed one of the most technical yet central dimensions of the project: the need for reliable, integrated, and interoperable data. It generated 27 views and 117 impressions. The value of this video lies in the fact that it helped communicate a key technical backbone of the project in a form more accessible than a written methodological explanation.

Figure 26: "Building the VeriFish Knowledge Base: Why Reliable Fisheries Data Matters" Interview video with Yannis Marketakis

4.7.2.3. *External Advisory Board Voices*¹⁰

This short series featured members of the VeriFish External Advisory Board representing research, industry, market actors, and policy expertise. The videos focused on the need for verifiable indicators, shared definitions, and improved data interoperability.

Featured experts included:

- [David Bassett \(General Secretary, European Aquaculture Technology & Innovation Platform - EATIP\) with 14 views;](#)
- [Paul Bulcock \(Sustainable Fisheries Partnership\) 11 views;](#)
- [Pedro Reis Santos \(Market Advisory Council\) with 8 views.](#)

⁸ https://verifish.info/interactive-seafood-insights/#VeriFish_knowledge_Base

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cprlNQ3DWQs>

¹⁰ https://verifish.info/interactive-seafood-insights/#External_Advisory_Board_Voices

Figure 27: Preview “External Advisory Board Voices” Playlist on VeriFish YouTube Channel

This series was strategically important because it located VeriFish within a wider ecosystem of external validation and sector relevance. The campaign reinforced the message that the project’s concerns were not internal consortium priorities alone, but part of a broader need recognised by actors outside the partnership.

4.7.2.4. *Voices Behind the Indicators: Defining Responsible Seafood*¹¹

Recorded during the Catch Welfare Platform Conference in IJmuiden in November 2025, this seven-episode series gathered insights from welfare researchers, data specialists, supply-chain actors, and industry representatives. The episodes featured:

- [Christine Xu \(Aquatic Life Institute\)](#) - 15 views
- [Hoang Nguyen \(Vietnam Tuna Association\)](#) - 6 views
- [Irene Kranendonk \(Fish Tales\)](#) - 13 views
- [Miguel Ruano \(Sustainable Fisheries Partnership\)](#) - 14 views
- [Pieke Molenaar \(Wageningen Marine Research\)](#) - 25 views
- [Udo Censkowsky \(Bluesensus\)](#) - 19 views
- [Wasseem Emam \(Ethical Seafood Research\)](#) - 29 views

¹¹ https://verifish.info/interactive-seafood-insights/#Voices_Behind_the_Indicators

Figure 28: Preview “Voices Behind the Indicators: Defining Responsible Seafood” Playlist on VeriFish YouTube Channel

This was one of the most thematically coherent and strategically relevant video series produced by the project, because it connected VeriFish to current debates on welfare, traceability, transparency, and measurable sustainability.

4.7.2.5. A VeriFish Story¹²

The storytelling strand of the video work focused on fishers and the lived reality of fisheries, offering a more human-centred complement to the expert and explainer videos.

The published stories featured:

- [Mario Bartulin from Croatia](#) - “Small- Scale Fishing in the Adriatic” - 24 views
- [Branko Matković from Croatia](#) - “Small- Scale Fishing in the Adriatic” - 18 views
- [Máté Juhász from Hungary](#) - “Can fishing help protect native fish species?” - 17 views

¹² https://verifish.info/interactive-seafood-insights/#VeriFish_Storytelling_Campaign

Figure 29: Preview “VeriFish Story” Playlist on VeriFish YouTube Channel

These videos were important because they connected the project’s communication not only to indicators and frameworks, but also to the people and realities that make transparent seafood communication necessary.

4.7.2.6. The VeriFish Indicator Framework:

Dedicated explainer videos were produced to communicate the core pillars of the project, namely the socio-economic, nutritional, and environmental dimensions of seafood sustainability.

Among these:

- [Simplifying Seafood Sustainability with VeriFish](#) - this video obtained the strongest performance, with 177 views, making it the most viewed video on the channel
- [VeriFish, Turning Catch Welfare into measurable action](#) - 78 views
- [The socio-economic pillar explainer](#) - 40 views
- [Why public, holistic sustainability data matters](#) - Paul Bulcock - 11 views
- [Fighting greenwashing and supporting informed seafood markets](#) - Pedro Reis Santos - 8 views

These figures show a clear pattern: videos that translated the broad project logic into a direct, understandable message performed better than narrower or more specialised pieces. That is exactly what one would expect, and it reinforces the argument that explainer content was one of the most effective formats within the video strategy.

Finally, even though it was not produced by VeriFish, [the Euronews Ocean episode](#) featuring project representatives should also be noted as a high-value visibility output, since it extended the project’s reach far beyond its own channels and achieved approximately 332,000 views.

4.7.2.7. *KPIs and observed performance*

To monitor the reach and impact of the video campaigns, VeriFish tracked a set of basic YouTube KPIs. Across the channel, the video series generated 663 total views, 8.9 hours of watch time and 5,100 impressions.

The KPI pattern also showed that videos with a clear explanatory purpose and accessible framing performed better than narrower or more technical pieces. This supports the project's decision to prioritise short explainer and interview-led formats as a way of making complex sustainability information easier to understand and more adaptable to different dissemination contexts.

Table 2: Overview of the main video series and audiovisual formats produced under Subtask 3.1.5, including their communication purpose, thematic focus, main audiences, dissemination channels, and indicative performance data.

Video series / format	Main purpose	Main content focus	Distribution and hosting	Audience mainly addressed	Illustrative performance data
VeriFish trailer and short video series (overall)	To translate complex project content into accessible visual communication and support the project's digital dissemination strategy	Seafood sustainability across environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional dimensions; responsible decision-making; visibility of project outputs and messages	Hosted primarily on the official VeriFish YouTube channel and further promoted through social media, newsletters, website content, and event-related communication	Professional stakeholders, researchers, policy and sector audiences, as well as broader non-technical publics reached through simplified visual formats	28 videos published, 663 total views, 8.2 hours watch time, 5100 impressions, 3.2% impressions click-through rate, 22 subscribers gained
2 Questions, 6 Perspectives	To communicate core project ideas through short expert testimonies using a common interview structure	Why sustainability in fisheries and aquaculture matters today and how VeriFish contributes to awareness on sustainable seafood	YouTube, social media cross-promotion, website and campaign-related communication	Professional stakeholders, project-related communities, sustainability and seafood audiences	Michelle Boonstra 31 views, Ixai Salvo 17, Themistoklis Altintzoglou 14, Christine Absil 10, Tim Huntington 7, and Siân Astley 5
Building the VeriFish Knowledge Base: Why Reliable Fisheries Data Matters	To explain one of the project's most technical components in an understandable way	Architecture of the knowledge base, verified data aggregation, transparency, support for decision-making	YouTube and cross-platform dissemination	Researchers, technical stakeholders, data-oriented audiences, policy and supply-chain actors	27 views, 117 impressions
External Advisory Board Voices	To provide external validation and broaden the credibility of the project through recognised external experts	Need for verifiable indicators, common definitions, data interoperability, broader sector relevance	YouTube and social media promotion	Professional audiences, policy and market actors, research and advisory communities	Series published with David Bassett 14 views, Paul Bulcock 11, and Pedro Reis Santos 8

Voices Behind the Indicators: Defining Responsible Seafood	To connect VeriFish to current debates on welfare, transparency, and measurable sustainability through event-based interviews	Catch welfare, traceability, fisheries innovation, industry practice, ethical seafood, structured sustainability	Recorded at the Catch Welfare Platform Conference in IJmuiden and disseminated through YouTube and project channels	Sector stakeholders, researchers, fisheries and welfare communities, professional audiences	Wasseem Emam 29 views, Pieke Molenaar 25, Udo Censkowsky 19, Miguel Ruano 14, Christine Xu 15, Irene Kranendonk 13, Hoang Nguyen 6
A VeriFish Story	To humanise the project through fisher-centred storytelling and lived experience	Fisheries realities, adaptation, practical experience, the human side of sustainability communication	YouTube and project dissemination channels	Citizens, consumers, educators, fisheries stakeholders, broader audiences interested in real-world stories	Mario Bartulin 24 views, Branko Matković 18, Máté Juhász 17
The VeriFish Indicator Framework: 3 Sustainability Pillars	To explain the project’s three core pillars and simplify the overall indicator logic	Socio-economic, nutritional, and environmental pillars; broader project explainers; catch welfare and public data relevance	YouTube, website integration, social media promotion, use in dissemination campaigns	Broad project audiences, including non-technical users needing an accessible entry point into the framework	Simplifying Seafood Sustainability with VeriFish: 177; VeriFish – Turning catch welfare into measurable action: 78 views; Socio-economic pillar explainer: 40 views; Nutritional pillar explainer: 7 Why public, holistic sustainability data matters: 8 views; Fighting greenwashing and supporting informed seafood markets: 7 views

4.8. Subtask 3.1.6 Scientific publications and technical dissemination

Subtask 3.1.6 covered the scientific publications and technical dissemination activities that supported the scientific credibility, transparency, and longer-term impact of VeriFish. While much of WP3 focused on public-facing communication, stakeholder engagement, and outreach media products, this dimension ensured that the project also maintained a clear presence within the research and innovation community. Through scientific publications, conference contributions, posters, and technically oriented dissemination outputs, VeriFish extended its reach beyond general communication channels and engaged with specialised audiences interested in aquafood sustainability, data integration, knowledge representation, semantic technologies, and evidence-based communication. This was important because the project's credibility depended not only on making its outputs accessible, but also on showing that its methodologies and conceptual approach could withstand discussion and scrutiny in recognised scientific and technical environments.

The scientific footprint of the project included both peer-reviewed and conference-based contributions. In reverse chronological order, the publications and technical dissemination outputs acknowledging the support of VeriFish were as follows:

- Yannis Marketakis, Yannis Tzitzikas, Alessandro Petrocelli, Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Siân Astley, Christine Absil, Michelle Boonstra, Tim Huntington, Tracy Murai, Nicolas Baily. “Construction, Access, and Application of a Knowledge Base for Sustainable Aquafood Communication”. In proceedings of the 14th International Joint Conference, IJCKG 2025, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, October 15–17, 2025. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-95-5009-8_25
- Iordanis Sapidis, Valantis Zervos, Michalis Mountantonakis, Yannis Tzitzikas. “Interactive and Provenance-aware Search and QA over Documents using LLMs, RAG and Knowledge Graph Verbalization”. In: Balke, WT., et al. New Trends in Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries. TPDL 2025. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 2694. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-06136-2_24
- Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Ixai Salvo Borda, Alessandro Petrocelli, Christine Absil, Michelle Boonstra, Tim Huntington, Yannis Marketakis, Siân Astley, Karl Presser, Petter Olsen. “VeriFish: The Sustainability Indicator Framework to Communicate Responsible Aquafood Production and Consumption Patterns”. ePoster in Aquaculture Europe 2025, Valencia, Spain, September 2025 https://aquaeas.org/pdf/AE2025_PinkPages.pdf
- Yannis Marketakis, Yannis Tzitzikas, Aureliano Gentile, Anton Ellenbroek, Marc Taconet. “Building a Global Aquatic Resources Knowledge Base for Fisheries”. In proceedings of 11th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies in Agriculture, Food & Environment (HAICTA 2024), Samos, Greece, October 2024. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:272270834>.

These outputs demonstrate that VeriFish contributed actively to the advancement of knowledge in at least two interrelated domains. On the one hand, the project addressed questions related to sustainable aquafood communication and the development of a structured indicator framework capable of linking environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional dimensions. On the other, it contributed to more

technical fields such as semantic technologies, knowledge bases, provenance-aware information access, and data interoperability. This dual scientific profile is significant because it reflects the real nature of the project. This scientific and technical dissemination dimension supported the project in ways that general public communication alone could not. First, it reinforced the credibility of VeriFish by ensuring that its approaches and technical architecture were exposed to peer and expert review in recognised scientific venues. Second, it extended the reach of the project towards specialised audiences who are relevant for longer-term methodological uptake, replication, or further research. Third, it positioned VeriFish within wider academic and innovation discussions, helping the project become part of ongoing conversations about sustainable food systems, responsible seafood communication, and the use of semantic and AI-supported tools for knowledge organisation and access. In this sense, scientific dissemination did not duplicate the role of public communication. It complemented it by speaking to audiences whose interest lies in methodological validity, technical implementation, and future research potential.

4.9. Monitoring and KPI assessment for T3.1

Monitoring under Task 3.1 combined platform-specific analytics with project-level tracking tools. In line with the Grant Agreement, VeriFish monitored its digital platforms throughout the project in order to understand how published content performed, how audiences responded, and how communication results evolved over time. In practice, this included Google Analytics for the website, native analytics from LinkedIn and the other social media platforms, YouTube analytics for the video series, newsletter records and subscriber tracking, and publication or repository tracking for scientific and technical dissemination, including Open Access availability through Zenodo where relevant was necessary because T3.1 covered several channels and formats, each of which required different indicators to assess visibility, engagement, and uptake.

The Grant Agreement defined several communication KPIs for the wider project campaign, including website sessions, social media followers, newsletter publication, and participation in external events. The results available for T3.1 show that the main digital communication targets were met or exceeded. The website target was set at more than 1,000 sessions by month 12 and more than 3,000 by month 24. Based on the available analytics period, the website reached 7,331 sessions and 4,990 total users, clearly surpassing the final target. The target for social media followers was 500 by month 12 and 1,000 by month 24, while the project reached a combined total of 1,146 followers across LinkedIn, Instagram, X, Facebook, and Bluesky. For newsletters, the target was 4 by month 12 and 12 by month 24. By 13 April 2026, VeriFish had published 12 newsletters, with one additional final newsletter prepared for circulation at the end of the project. Overall, these results show that the core communication outputs planned under T3.1 were not only delivered, but maintained consistently throughout the action.

Table 3: Concise summary of the main verified KPI results for T3.1 (Date: 15/04/2026)

KPI area	Grant Agreement target	Verified result	Assessment
Website sessions	>1,000 by M12; >3,000 by M24	7,331 sessions	Exceeded

Website users	Not specified as headline KPI, but monitored as awareness metric	4,990 total users	Strong visibility result
Social media followers across platforms	500 by M12; 1,000 by M24	1,146 followers	Exceeded
Newsletters published	4 by M12; 12 by M24	12 published by 30/04/2026	Achieved
Eurofish Magazine articles	Minimum 5 articles	7 published	Exceeded
YouTube/video output	4 short video trailers originally envisaged	28 videos published, plus 1 in final production	Exceeded in output volume
YouTube views	Not explicitly quantified in GA KPI table	661 total views	Modest but meaningful for a specialised audience
Scientific publications and technical dissemination outputs	Not expressed as a numeric KPI in the campaign table, but explicitly foreseen under T3.1	4 verified scientific/technical outputs	Delivered

Table 4: Functional differentiation summary of the different communication channel or format

Communication channel or format	Main contribution
Website	Awareness, discoverability, access to resources, destination for campaigns and event follow-up
LinkedIn	Professional engagement, click-through to outputs, visibility among relevant stakeholder communities
Instagram, X, Facebook, Bluesky	Supporting awareness and campaign amplification, especially for visual or lighter public-facing content
Newsletter	Retention, continuity, structured updates for an already interested audience
Eurofish Magazine	Durable communication towards professional and market-oriented audiences
Videos	Accessible explanation, narrative communication, reusable audiovisual dissemination
Scientific publications and technical outputs	Credibility, expert reach, methodological visibility
Events and stakeholder meetings	Direct contact, validation, discussion, networking, policy visibility

In terms of substantive stakeholder interaction, the channels that produced the strongest results were those that created reasons for audiences to go beyond simple exposure. The website generated substantive interaction when users landed directly on project output pages rather than only on the homepage. LinkedIn generated more than visibility when posts drove clicks towards outputs, registration pages, or public resources. The newsletter supported repeated contact with a smaller but more engaged audience. Eurofish Magazine articles provided deeper contextual communication to professional readers. Scientific publications and technical dissemination extended the project's reach into specialised research and innovation communities, reinforcing scientific credibility in ways that general public communication could not. Taken together, this suggests a clear division of function within T3.1: social media and the website were strongest for awareness, LinkedIn and video-supported output promotion were strongest for engagement, while newsletters, magazine articles, scientific publications, and output-linked website pages contributed more to deeper stakeholder interaction and longer-term credibility.

5. Task 3.2 – Requirements gathering phase for outreach media products

5.1. Task objectives and relevance

This task aimed at introducing collaborative mechanisms to assess the various media products to be delivered by WP3. At least 3 requirements gathering and design workshops were planned with representatives of different stakeholders to assess the media product under design, in order to build them in a collaborative manner and ensure a perfect match between the needs and the products implemented.

5.2. Four requirements gathering sessions

Four requirement gathering workshops were indeed organised during the project timeframe to collect inputs and specifications for the media products. The first one was organised in Heraklion, Crete, on the 20th of March 2025 in conjunction with the second VeriFish consortium meeting. A second online session was organised on 24th April to assess a few outstanding aspects. A benchmark analysis was also performed, with the objective of understanding which other similar products have been produced so far, collect successful examples from which good practices might be adopted and assess how the information on sustainability aspects have been included. High level results from this analysis were included in D3.3 VeriFish Media Products Requirements & Specification Document and reported in the *Technical Report for Year 1*.

The other two requirement gathering workshops were organised with stakeholders external to the VeriFish Consortium.

The third requirement gathering workshop was organised within the remit of the 3rd Catch Welfare Platform Conference, that brought together global experts, fishers, scientists, and innovators at Forteiland IJmuiden to discuss the future of wild-caught fish welfare. The VeriFish project played an active role as was featured in the scientific programme, with a presentation by Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT Services), and as it organised a specific stakeholder engagement session. On Day 2 of the conference, VeriFish hosted a dedicated working lunch¹³, bringing together key stakeholders from the seafood sector — including fishers, retailers, researchers, and sustainability experts — to discuss the role of structured indicators in communicating fish welfare and sustainability.

This closed session provided a unique opportunity to:

- Share feedback on the VeriFish Sustainability Indicator Framework
- Explore practical tools for transparent seafood communication
- Identify common challenges in aligning scientific data with real-world commercial needs
- Strengthen collaboration across sectors committed to responsible fishing practices

¹³ <https://verifish.info/verifish-at-the-catch-welfare-platform-conference-2025-spotlight-on-sustainability-and-communication/>

Participants were chosen on a voluntary basis from the list of participants to the Catch Welfare Conference, paying attention to ensure a variety of stakeholder types. 20 participants joined the working lunch, coming from the following Institutes and countries. Participants were also offered with reimbursement for their travel costs.

Table 5: List of organisations of the participants to the VeriFish working lunch

Organisation	Type	Country
Scottish White Fish Producer's Association	Fishery	United Kingdom
Welfare Footprint Institute	Research/NGO	Brazil
Lake Bounty Group / Uganda Fish Processors and Exporters Association (UFPEA) / Uganda National Women Fish Organisation (UNWFO)	Fishery	Uganda
Optimar AS	Technology	Norway
Vietnam Tuna Association - NGO and tuna industry association	Fishery	Vietnam
Shellfish Association of Great Britain	Other	United Kingdom
National Federation of Fishermen's Organisations	Fishery	United Kingdom
Shellfish Association of Great Britain	Other	United Kingdom
Nausicaa	Other	France
Associated Seafoods Ltd	Commerce	United Kingdom
CatchCam Technologies	Commerce	United Kingdom
Fish Tales	Commerce	Netherlands
Wild 'n Zilt	Fishery	Netherlands
Orkney Crab Limited	Other	UK
Community Catch	Fishery	UK
Scottish Fishermen's Federation	Fishery	UK
Sea Farms Ltd	Commerce	UK
Scottish Pelagic Fishermen's Association	Fishery	UK
De Nederlandse Vissersbond	Fishery	Netherlands

As reported in the table above, the session brought together a highly specialised group of stakeholders, including producers and processors such as Optimar AS, Associated Seafoods Ltd, Orkney Crab Limited, Sea Farms Ltd, Fish Tales, and Wild 'n Zilt; associations and NGOs such as the Scottish White Fish Producers Association, Scottish Fishermen's Federation, Scottish Pelagic Fishermen's Association, National Federation of Fishermen's Organisations, Shellfish Association of Great Britain, De Nederlandse Vissersbond, Vietnam Tuna Association, Lake Bounty Group and related African organisations, the Welfare Footprint Institute, and Community Catch; and innovation actors such as CatchCam Technologies.

A gathering form was distributed to participants that were asked to compile it during the lunch, while a guided presentation was given by VeriFish partners to facilitate their understanding of the questions and contextualising the work. The focus of the feedback session was the VeriFish web-app, including its usefulness and in particular the assessment of the process for contributing Tier 2 data to the app.

First, baseline operational data were collected, including targeted species, fishing areas, gear types, vessel characteristics, existing sustainability and quality certifications, and participation in Fishery Improvement Projects. Second, stakeholders supplied climate-related operational data, including vessel engine power

and annual fuel consumption. Third, ecological impact-related feedback was gathered on measures to mitigate habitat degradation, reduce bycatch of endangered, threatened, and protected species, and support gear recovery initiatives. Fourth, information was collected on the adoption of validated systems for humane stunning and killing practices. This structured interaction generated useful primary input for testing and refining the framework while also grounding the project more firmly in operational realities.

The figure shows three pages of a form titled 'VeriFish'.
 Page 5: 'Calling for producers information on sustainable fishery: purpose of this working lunch at Catch Welfare 2025 Conference'. It includes an introduction, the purpose of the working lunch, and a sign-up section with fields for 'Name, Surname and email*', 'Company Name*', and 'Provide your logo*'.
 Page 6: 'Company details'. It contains three sections: 'What species are you fishing?', 'Which are your fishing areas?', and 'What gear type do you use?'.
 Page 7: 'Step 2: Ecological Impact'. It includes a table with '2.1 HABITAT IMPACT' and 'Notes / suggestions'. The table contains questions about habitat impact measures and gear adaptation options.

Figure 30: Sample pages of the form used during the Working lunch at the Catch Welfare platform Annual event, November 2025

Figure 31: The Working Lunch during the Catch Welfare Annual Conference, IJmuiden, The Netherlands, November 2026

The conversations that took place during the working lunch reinforced the importance of co-design, clarity, and comparability in the next generation of seafood sustainability tools — principles at the core of the VeriFish approach. The feedback was collected and organised in a review document and passed to the VeriFish partners working on the development of the web-app (mainly COMMpla) that implemented the suggested changes. In particular, the online form for uploading Tier 2 data was edited according to the feedback received.

The last validation workshop was organised back-to-back with the VeriFish final conference on March 11¹⁴, 2026. The session was explicitly designed as a structured feedback session on three project outputs: the VeriFish web app, the guidelines for seafood value-chain actors, and the media/public engagement tools. Participants were organised into small groups invited to nominate a scribe and provide group inputs via Slido.

Figure 32: One of the working groups during the validation workshop in Brussels

Two sessions were run in a breakout mode, to allow all conference participants to join at least one of the two. The workshop was moderated by Sian Astley, EUROFIR, who guided the groups in responding to the following questions targeting the VeriFish media products, namely the VeriFish web-app, the VeriFish

¹⁴ <https://verifish.info/verifish-final-event/>

Guidelines and the Overfished! Card game and the poster on gear type that were physically available in the room:

- Q. What works well?
- Q. What is confusing or unclear?
- What is missing?
- Q. One key improvement
- Dot-Matrix Synthesis
- What one feature would make it better?
- Q. Are the guidelines clear?
- Q. Are they practical for value-chain actors?
- Q. What might prevent their use?
- Q. One key improvement
- Dot-Matrix Synthesis
- What one feature would make them better?
- Q. Are the materials easy to understand?
- Q. Which tool is most engaging?

Figure 33: Participants to the Validation workshop in Brussels, assessing the Gear Type poster

Figure 34: Example of feedback received on the VeriFish web-app and Guidelines

Also in this case, the feedback was passed to COMMpla and Eurofish partners to consider them while further evolving the content, design and user experience of the web-app, the VeriFish Guidelines and of the Overfished! Card game.

6. Task 3.3 – Prototype of the VeriFish web app (COMMpla)

6.1. Task objectives and communication relevance

Task 3.3 focused on the development of the VeriFish web application as a user-oriented tool designed to facilitate access to useful information on seafood and aquaculture consumption choices. Its purpose was to make complex sustainability-related information, including environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional dimensions, more accessible, verifiable, and usable for different audiences across the seafood value chain. In practical terms, the application was conceived as a means of bridging the gap between scientific knowledge and everyday decision-making by translating indicator-based information into a format that could support more informed choices at the point of purchase, communication, or consumption.

The communication relevance of the app goes beyond its technical function as a digital product. The application acts as a translation layer between the VeriFish Knowledge Base and end users, transforming fragmented and heterogeneous datasets into a more coherent and navigable user experience. The app puts the VeriFish indicator framework into practice through a clear digital interface in which information can be explored in a structured and intelligible way. In doing so, it supports one of the central aims of VeriFish, namely, to standardise how seafood sustainability information is communicated and to reduce ambiguity in the way evidence is presented to different users. The app therefore functions as one of the main operational expressions of the project's wider communication logic.

6.2. From specifications to prototype

The development of the VeriFish web application was guided directly by the technical and functional requirements defined in Deliverable D3.2. The architecture and interface were shaped through a user-centred design approach informed by stakeholder co-design workshops and requirements gathering activities carried out under WP3. This was important because the challenge for the app was not simply to display data, but to balance scientific depth with usability and to make complex sustainability and nutritional information understandable for users with very different backgrounds, needs, and expectations.

Figure 35: VeriFish App front page

The intended user journey was designed to connect producers, intermediaries, and consumers through a relatively simple pathway into more detailed information. One of the intended access routes was through QR-code-based interaction, allowing fishers and aquaculture producers to register on the platform, submit relevant data, and generate a personalised QR code linked to a validated factsheet. Through this mechanism, producers could communicate aspects of their practices and products more directly to downstream users. For consumers and other users, the main journey involved either searching for a species by common name or accessing linked information through QR codes at the point of purchase or consumption. This made it possible to retrieve connected datasets and insights on seafood provenance, environmental aspects, and nutritional value in a form that was much easier to navigate than the underlying data sources themselves.

The application relies on the VeriFish Knowledge Base as its authoritative backend. In this architecture, the web app functions as the operational front end, while the Knowledge Base aggregates and harmonises verified FAIR data from trusted global sources such as the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries, FishBase, and EuroFIR. To support performance and usability, the system also made use of a backend caching layer implemented in Supabase, which stores a local copy of the relevant data. This improved performance by reducing repeated requests to external sources and made data retrieval faster and more stable. It also increased the practical robustness of the application in situations of limited or intermittent connectivity,

which is relevant in fisheries and other operational environments where constant online access cannot be assumed.

6.3. App content and user-facing features

The application organises information into detailed but readable species factsheets that bring together multiple data categories in a single user-facing environment. The aim was to provide a more holistic view of seafood products by combining biological, environmental, socio-economic, provenance, certification, and nutritional dimensions within one navigable interface.

The information made available through the application includes biological data such as scientific names, common names in multiple European languages, and species images. It also provides fish stock and fisheries-related information, including provenance data such as FAO fishing areas, production methods, and fishing gear where relevant. Environmental and socio-economic information is integrated through indicator-related data and certification references, while food composition data includes nutritional profiles covering macronutrients and selected micronutrients relevant to seafood, together with dietary reference information and health-related metrics. Recipes from the VeriFish cookbook are also linked directly to species pages, thereby connecting species-level information with practical food preparation and use.

Figure 36: VeriFish App menu and information for a species

A key feature of the application is the way it translates the multi-dimensional VeriFish framework into a more intuitive digital experience. When a user selects a species, the factsheet is segmented into the main content areas corresponding to the project logic, including biological information, environmental aspects, nutrition, and socio-economic information. Nutritional content is further supported through comparative

presentation of values across preparation methods, such as raw, cooked, or canned. This structure makes it possible for users to gain a quick overview while still allowing more detailed exploration where needed.

Navigation was designed to remain as simple as possible despite the complexity of the underlying information. Search functionality allows users to perform multi-parameter queries, including species name, language, FAO fishing area, and fishing method, with progressive refinement and typeahead suggestions helping to make the experience more predictable and accessible. Following expert testing, the final release of the app included a redesigned user interface aimed at maximising simplicity by removing unnecessary filters and improving the clarity of the user journey.

6.4. Initial and final releases

The development of the VeriFish web app progressed through two main stages, namely the initial prototype release documented in Deliverable D3.4 and the final release documented in Deliverable D3.5. The transition between these two stages involved both technical and user-facing improvements.

One of the most significant changes between the initial and final versions was a major architectural upgrade in the backend data layer. The system was migrated from Firebase/Firestore to Supabase with PostgreSQL in order to overcome limitations in query structure and relational data handling. This transition enabled more complex multi-dimensional filtering, improved management of linked data, and supported more structured analytics and performance.

The final release also introduced additional content and data integration, including Marine Stewardship Council certification data and STECF-related sources, as well as a more developed nutritional heat map across preparation methods and an expanded set of socio-economic, environmental, and aquaculture indicators. At the same time, the application was refined through expert review and testing. Based on this feedback, the final version featured a substantially redesigned user interface intended to improve navigation, reduce unnecessary complexity, and optimise loading times. These changes were important because they moved the application closer to its intended role as a practical user-facing dissemination tool rather than a technically impressive but difficult-to-use prototype.

6.5. The app as a dissemination and engagement tool

The VeriFish web application was developed as one of the project's main dissemination and engagement tools. Its value lies in the fact that it bridges the gap between the existence of scientific data and the practical usability of that data by non-specialist and mixed audiences. The app supports awareness and understanding of VeriFish results by presenting environmental, socio-economic, and nutritional information in a more standardised and accessible way.

Its dissemination and engagement value is also reflected in the way it was presented and discussed with stakeholders. A key presentation moment took place during the working lunch held in connection with the Catch Welfare Platform conference in IJmuiden in November 2025, and a further important opportunity for presentation and validation occurred during the VeriFish final event in Brussels in March 2026. On these occasions, the app was shown to producer organisations, industry associations,

technology providers, researchers, and other stakeholders. The direct feedback received during these sessions helped validate the usability of the tool and informed further refinements. In addition, the consortium received approximately 90 direct requests for access to the VeriFish web app, indicating interest from a broad range of stakeholders, including industry actors, NGOs, research organisations, and educational institutions. This is important because it shows that the application was not only completed as a deliverable but also recognised by external users as a relevant and potentially useful resource.

Figure 37: VeriFish App with producers QR code and information

6.6. Examples of indicator framework implementation through the app

The app provides one of the clearest examples of how the VeriFish indicator framework was implemented in practice. This can be seen clearly in the treatment of nutritional information, where food composition data are simplified through a visual heat map comparing nutritional values across preparation methods. It is also visible in the way biological information is presented, with taxonomy, species images, FAO fishing areas, and fishing gear or aquaculture production methods displayed in a more intelligible format than would be possible through raw datasets alone. Environmental and socio-economic aspects are also made visible by integrating authoritative sources such as STECF and by displaying certification and related information through a consistent user interface. In this sense, the app does not merely contain the framework. It operationalises it by showing how different indicator domains can be brought together in one practical communication environment.

Figure 38: VeriFish App with Environmental scores and Nutritional scores displayed

Figure 39: VeriFish app, stories from producers

6.7. Main lessons from T3.3

Task 3.3 shows that the VeriFish application functioned both as a dissemination tool and as a technological demonstrator, but its longer-term significance lies in its potential as a strategic asset for exploitation beyond the lifetime of the project. With its public release on the web and publication on the Apple App Store and Google Play Store in April 2026, the app moved from being a prototype within the project to becoming a communication and access tool with possible future use beyond the immediate project context.

Its design supports this longer-term potential because it is based on an open and scalable architecture combining API-based access, semantic web integration, a robust backend infrastructure, and the VeriFish Knowledge Base. This means the app is a tool that can evolve over time and be connected to future datasets, new species coverage, and new communication needs. In that respect, one of the strongest lessons from the task is that digital tools of this type have value only if they are built with future interoperability and extension in mind.

A second lesson is the importance of expanding data coverage and language support. The application is inherently scalable and could be extended to include additional external sources, a wider range of species, more fisheries and aquaculture systems, and broader geographic contexts. Further language development would also improve accessibility for more diverse stakeholders across the seafood value chain. This flexibility is one of the main strengths of the app and should be considered a priority in any future development scenario.

A third lesson concerns Tier 2 data collection and direct producer input. One of the most important opportunities for future improvement lies in strengthening the submission modules that would allow fishers and aquaculture producers to provide first-hand and potentially real-time data from vessels or farms in a practical way. Improving this functionality would support a more continuous flow of high-quality data and strengthen the direct and verifiable link between producers and the wider seafood value chain. In that sense, the future value of the app lies not only in what it already displays, but in its potential to become a more dynamic interface between structured data, real-world practice, and seafood communication.

6.8. Subtask 3.4.2 VeriFish factsheets

The VeriFish factsheets constituted one of the core user-facing information formats of the project and were designed to provide a clear and accessible overview of the main sustainability dimensions associated with seafood species. Their primary purpose was to translate a complex, multi-source data infrastructure into integrated and decision-oriented insights that could support communication and understanding of environmental, nutritional, and socio-economic indicators. In this sense, the factsheets played a central role in operationalising the VeriFish framework, since they transformed the underlying data architecture into a format that could be used more directly by non-technical and mixed audiences.

The factsheets were hosted within the VeriFish web and mobile application and were made accessible through a searchable digital catalogue as well as through scannable QR codes generated by fishers and producers. This made them a flexible communication tool capable of functioning both as part of a digital browsing experience and as an access point linked to specific products or producers. Their initial development and release were aligned with Milestone 7, which marked the first version of the VeriFish factsheets and the successful integration of the indicator framework into a practical digital format.

The factsheets were designed to serve different stakeholder groups across the seafood value chain, including consumers, fishers, aquaculture producers, retailers, and policymakers. Because these users do not have the same information needs, the content was structured in a dual format. A lighter factsheet view provided a concise overview of the main headline indicators of the framework, allowing users to

obtain a quick and intuitive understanding of the key information. A fuller factsheet view, accessible through a dedicated page and expandable sections, provided more detailed and multidimensional content for users wishing to explore the underlying information in greater depth. This layered structure was important because it allowed the project to accommodate both quick consultation and more detailed exploration without forcing all users into the same level of complexity.

By relying on a clear structure and intuitive visual presentation, the factsheets made it possible for users to interpret key data more rapidly and with less need for prior scientific expertise. In this respect, they served as one of the most direct examples of how the VeriFish framework was translated into a communication product capable of making complex sustainability-related information more usable in real-world contexts.

Figure 40: VeriFish Factsheet as it can be seen in the VeriFish App

7. Task 3.4 – Media products & stakeholder engagement campaigns (Trust-IT)

7.1. Subtask 3.4.1 Community of Practice maintenance and animation

The VeriFish Community of Practice served as a central stakeholder platform through which industry experts, researchers, policymakers, civil society actors, and interested citizens could engage with the project and contribute to the development, discussion, and validation of its outputs. Its role within WP3 was not limited to passive information sharing. Rather, the Community of Practice was intended as a structured environment for cross-sectoral collaboration, feedback collection, testing, and exchange around the sustainability, traceability, nutritional value, and communication of seafood products. In this sense, it functioned both as a dissemination mechanism and as a co-creation space through which the project could expose its concepts and tools to external scrutiny and strengthen their relevance for future users.

To support differentiated participation, the Community of Practice offered several pathways for involvement. Members could provide targeted feedback on the draft indicator framework, take part in strategic discussions related to sustainable aquafood communication, remain informed about project milestones and events, and become part of a wider European and international network interested in more transparent and responsible seafood communication. This flexible structure was important because the project needed different kinds of engagement from different actors. Some stakeholders were relevant as validators of technical content, others as potential multipliers, and others as informed users of the project's evolving outputs.

7.1.1. Stakeholder Recruitment, Maintenance, and Activation

During the initial phase of the project, stakeholders were recruited through targeted outreach conducted by consortium members, who relied on their existing professional networks, institutional contacts, and thematic expertise. This approach was necessary because VeriFish needed to build a community that reflected the diversity of the seafood communication ecosystem rather than relying only on open and generic expressions of interest. The recruitment strategy prioritised seafood retailers and producers, including aquaculture actors and associations, consumers and consumer associations, policy stakeholders and funding agencies, standard development organisations and good-practice entities, representatives linked to initiatives such as Taste the Ocean and Farm to Fork, research organisations, NGOs, and other relevant EU projects.

To facilitate onboarding, a dedicated webpage¹⁵ was launched on the VeriFish website. This portal streamlined the subscription process and allowed the consortium to consolidate existing contacts with newly recruited stakeholders into a more unified stakeholder base. Maintenance and activation of the Community of Practice were then supported through a continuous digital communication strategy. Dedicated emails were sent periodically to invite new members, keep registered stakeholders informed

¹⁵ <https://verifish.info/community-of-practice/>

about project progress, and direct attention towards upcoming events, milestones, and outputs. These communications also encouraged further interaction with the wider project ecosystem, including the VeriFish newsletter, social media channels, web application, and media products. In this sense, the Community of Practice was not maintained as an isolated database, but as an active extension of the broader communication and stakeholder engagement strategy.

A particularly important moment in the activation and qualitative deepening of the Community of Practice took place during the Catch Welfare Platform Conference¹⁶ in IJmuiden, the Netherlands, in November 2025. At that stage of the project, an in-person working lunch was organised specifically to assess the VeriFish framework and gather direct input on capture fisheries indicators. The session brought together 20 selected participants, including producers, association representatives, technology providers, and researchers. This was a strategically important step because it moved the Community of Practice from remote and distributed interaction into direct, structured discussion with a highly relevant group of stakeholders whose expertise was closely aligned with the project's needs.

7.1.2. CoP Contributions: Feedback, Testing, and Validation

The Community of Practice contributed to VeriFish in several ways, particularly through feedback, testing, validation, dissemination, and visibility. Its most important contribution was to provide an organised channel through which external actors could react to project concepts and tools rather than merely receive them. This helped the consortium assess whether outputs such as the indicator framework, the web application, and the media products were understandable, relevant, and practically aligned with stakeholder expectations. The Community of Practice also increased the visibility of the project by creating a network of informed stakeholders who could follow developments, participate in activities, and in some cases further circulate the project's outputs through their own organisations and networks.

The IJmuiden working lunch organised during the Catch Welfare Platform (November 2025) provides the clearest example of this contribution. The session was explicitly structured to obtain direct stakeholder input, showcase the workflow of the web application, and secure practical validation. Through a customised data collection form, participants contributed across four parameters. The Community of Practice also contributed indirectly to advocacy and dissemination. By consenting to the use of their input and by engaging with project tools and materials, participating stakeholders helped strengthen the visibility and credibility of the VeriFish approach. This matters because stakeholder communities are valuable not simply for the number of names they contain, but for the extent to which they make project outputs more robust, more legitimate, and more grounded in real-world use conditions.

7.1.3. Assessment of Engagement

In quantitative terms, the VeriFish Community of Practice reached 207 active records by the reporting point, representing a broad mix of organisational entities and individual participants. Of these, 100 were recorded as individuals, with a gender distribution of 60 men and 40 women. Geographically, the Community of Practice demonstrated a clearly international profile, with the strongest representation coming from Italy, followed by the United Kingdom and France. Additional significant representation was

¹⁶ <https://verifish.info/verifish-at-the-catch-welfare-platform-conference-2025-spotlight-on-sustainability-and-communication/>

recorded from Spain, the United States, and Belgium, alongside members from a wider range of countries. This confirms that the Community of Practice extended beyond a narrow consortium-adjacent audience and attracted interest from a broader European and international ecosystem.

The Community of Practice also experienced significant growth in the later stages of the project, driven by the release of concrete outputs. In particular, the introduction of the VeriFish web application and the Overfished! card game acted as clear catalysts for new stakeholder activation. This was evident from January 2026 to the end of April 2026, when the consortium received **42 direct requests to access the VeriFish web app** and **69 direct requests for the Overfished! card game** and related media products. This pattern is important because it shows that engagement strengthened when the project moved from framework-building and explanation towards tangible public-facing tools. In plain terms, the Community of Practice became more active when stakeholders had something concrete to test, request, or use.

Figure 41: Distribution of VeriFish Community of Practice members by stakeholder category, showing a total of 154 participants across the main stakeholder groups represented in the initiative.

The profile of these requests also reveals the diversity of the engaged audience. Requests for the web app came from actors across industry and retail, NGOs, research and education, and consultancy environments. Examples included Skretting, the Danish Pelagic Producer Organisation, Hanos, Produmar, Simplymeats Traceable Distribution Inc., WWF Sweden, National Geographic, Europe Jacques Delors, the University of Florence, the University of Coimbra, the SUBMARINER Network, Atlantis Consulting, the Tagliacarne Study Centre, the Department of Education of the Government of Navarre, and the 1st High School of Chios. Requests for the Overfished! card game and related media products showed similar diversity, including international and European institutions such as FAO, CINEA, REA, and the Delegation of the European Union to the USA, as well as marine research and education bodies such as Ifremer, DTU Aqua, the Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries, CIIMAR, Florida Sea Grant, the Maine Aquaculture

Innovation Center, the Polytechnic University of Marche, and the Blue School project in Brazil. Industry, retail, and consultancy actors requesting the materials included Conxemar, EDEKA, Eurofish, AquaBioTech Group, Associated Seafoods Ltd, and Fugro.

Figure 42: Country of origin of members of the VeriFish Community of Practice, illustrating the international reach of the stakeholder community developed by the project.

Beyond the figures, the Community of Practice showed its strongest value when it functioned as a co-creation environment rather than as a mailing list. The inclusion of actors from across the seafood supply chain, from producers to policymakers, helped prevent the project from developing its outputs in an institutional or geographic silo. The practical feedback received during testing sessions directly informed refinements to the web application and contributed to the usability and relevance of the final results. The project succeeded in activating the right people at key moments and in using their input to make the outputs more credible, better grounded, and more relevant to real stakeholder needs.

7.2. Subtask 3.4.3 Children & citizens media products

Subtask 3.4.3 focused on the design and dissemination of educational and awareness-raising materials tailored to non-professional audiences, with particular attention to citizens, families, children, schools, and intermediaries involved in informal education or public outreach. The purpose of this subtask was to translate the logic of VeriFish into formats that could make seafood sustainability, seasonality, nutrition, fishing methods, and species diversity more understandable and more engaging for audiences unlikely to interact directly with technical reports, indicator frameworks, or specialist guidance documents. In this

sense, the subtask played an important role within WP3 by extending the project's communication beyond professional and institutional stakeholders and by creating tools through which broader publics could engage with the themes of responsible seafood production and consumption in practical, visual, and accessible ways and learn more about seafood, evoke curiosity, and familiarize them to seafood with the goal of increasing sustainable seafood consumption.

A defining feature of this subtask was the use of a white-label approach. The media products were developed in a format that allowed them to be disseminated and reused by consumer associations, schools, NGOs, seafood stakeholders, and other intermediaries with an interest in education and awareness-raising. All versions featured the VeriFish identity and the required acknowledgment of EU funding, while also allowing external organisations to request and reuse the materials for their own educational purposes. This approach was important because it increased the potential life of the materials beyond the immediate project channels and created conditions for further uptake by actors able to redistribute or adapt them in their own communication and teaching environments. To reinforce openness and accessibility, the materials were released under a Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 licence, and digital assets were hosted through the VeriFish website and Zenodo where relevant.

Several media products were developed under this subtask. One of the most important was the educational poster Fishing Methods at a Glance (Figure 43), which addressed seafood sustainability through one of its clearest and most tangible dimensions, namely the harvesting method. Rather than presenting sustainability in abstract terms, the poster introduced eight common fishing gears, including pelagic trawl, bottom trawl, pole-and-line, longlines, purse seine nets, boat seine nets, gillnets and entangling nets, and fykes, traps, and pots. Each method was accompanied by a short explanation of how the gear works and the species commonly associated with it. To make the content more understandable for non-specialist users, the poster also included a glossary explaining terms such as bycatch, ghost fishing, and schooling species. A QR code connected the printed material to the VeriFish app, allowing users to move from a static educational product to more detailed digital exploration. The content was synthesised from scientific and sectoral sources, including FAO, EMODnet Biology, GRSF, and IUCN, and the final poster was made available as a free printable PDF in eight languages through the VeriFish website¹⁷ and Zenodo¹⁸.

¹⁷ <https://verifish.info/verifish-fishing-methods-at-a-glance-poster/>

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/19898251>

Figure 43: :“Fishing Methods at a Glance” Poster

A second key output was the VeriFish seasonal seafood calendar, **Delicious and Nutritious Seafood on Your Plate All Year Long** (Figure 44 and Figure 45). This product was designed as a high-visibility and family-oriented communication tool that could introduce sustainability and seafood seasonality into everyday food-related contexts. Structured as a twelve-month calendar, it highlighted one species per month and combined a short species introduction with a sustainability snapshot, curiosities, and nutritional highlights. To increase practical relevance, each monthly sheet also included a recipe drawn from the VeriFish cookbook and QR codes linking users to the full preparation steps. This combination of seasonality, nutrition, and recipe-led content was particularly well suited to households and non-specialist audiences because it connected sustainability communication to ordinary food practices. The calendar was made available as a free printable PDF through the VeriFish website¹⁹ and Zenodo²⁰.

¹⁹ <https://verifish.info/verifish-calendar-seafood-inspiration-all-year-round/>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/19898965>

Figure 44: VeriFish Calendar Cover

Figure 45: VeriFish Calendar: January Factsheet

The **Overfished! card game**²¹ (Figure 46 and Figure 47) represented one of the most distinctive outputs of this subtask and provided a gamified approach to ocean literacy and sustainable seafood awareness. Designed for children and families, the game combined comic-style design with simple strategic mechanics and sustainability-oriented content. It consisted of 56 cards, including species cards and action cards, and encouraged players to think about seafood species, fishing practices, and responsible choices through play. The visual design highlighted key sustainability indicators in a simplified and memorable form, making it especially suitable for educational use in informal and semi-formal contexts. The game was made available in seven languages as a free printable PDF and was distributed through the VeriFish website upon request. This request-based model allowed the consortium to track demand while ensuring that the game reached stakeholders with a direct interest in using it.

²¹ <https://verifish.info/overfished-the-card-game-by-verifish/>

Figure 46: Overview of Overfished! Cards

Figure 47: Overfished! Instruction Booklet

The **VeriFish puzzle** (Figure 48) and its related digital poster version (Figure 19) complemented the above materials by focusing on species recognition and visual familiarity with marine biodiversity. Drawing directly from the VeriFish web app, the puzzle showcased more than 130 species together with their common and scientific names and served as a visually attractive resource for children and families interested in learning about fish identification and the morphology of marine life. To extend its educational value beyond the puzzle format itself, a QR code linked users directly to the VeriFish web app and website, enabling them to explore detailed factsheets for the species represented. As with the other materials, the puzzle and digital poster version were made available as free printable PDFs via the VeriFish website²² and Zenodo²³.

²² <https://verifish.info/discover-the-diversity-of-the-ocean-poster/>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/records/19898804>

Figure 48: VeriFish Puzzle

The release of these products was aligned with the corresponding milestone under WP3, and the materials were delivered on schedule. The first branded materials to become available were the Overfished! card game and the Fishing Methods at a Glance poster, both of which were made accessible through dedicated sections of the VeriFish website. The dissemination model combined open public access with targeted distribution depending on the product. The poster, calendar, and puzzle were made publicly downloadable for direct printing and reuse, while the card game was distributed through a request-based system that allowed the project to respond to specific expressions of interest and maintain some visibility over uptake. This combination of open access and targeted dissemination was appropriate because it balanced broad availability with a more controlled distribution model for the product that was most clearly designed as a reusable educational asset.

The usability and relevance of these products are reflected in the demand generated, especially for the Overfished! card game. By 24 April 2026, a total of 68 online requests for the game had been received and processed. The organisations requesting the game covered a wide range of sectors and geographies, including universities and academic institutions, research institutes, government bodies and public agencies, NGOs and non-profit initiatives, private companies, industry networks and associations, and educational projects and schools. Requesting organisations included, among others, DTU Aqua, Ifremer, CIIMAR, the European Commission, FAO, CINEA, Conxemar, EATiP, the University of Florence, the University of Guelph, AquaBioTech Group, and several schools and educational initiatives. This diversity matters because it shows that the product was not perceived only as a children’s game in a narrow sense,

but as a broader educational and outreach tool with relevance across academic, institutional, sectoral, and public-facing environments.

The geographic spread of requests further underlines this point. Demand came from countries across Europe, including Denmark, Sweden, Spain, Greece, Belgium, Italy, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, Ireland, Malta, Croatia, Latvia, Cyprus, Poland, and Norway, while also extending beyond Europe to countries such as Canada, the United States, Mexico, Brazil, Peru, Korea, and Mauritius. This confirms that a key factor of the success was the translation into different languages and contexts as well, allowing the target group to use the products in their native language.

Overall, Subtask 3.4.3 demonstrates that the VeriFish framework could be translated into media products capable of reaching non-specialist audiences in useful and engaging ways. The poster, calendar, card game, and puzzle did not attempt to reproduce the full complexity of the project's technical outputs. Instead, they selected specific entry points, such as fishing methods, seasonality, nutrition, species recognition, and playful learning, and used them to create educational pathways into the broader logic of responsible seafood communication. Their value lies precisely in this translation function. They made it possible for VeriFish to communicate beyond expert and institutional circles and to test whether sustainability-related information could be made accessible without being emptied of meaning.

7.3. Subtask 3.4.4 Food & nutrition products

Subtask 3.4.4 focused on the development of food- and nutrition-oriented media products designed to translate the VeriFish indicator framework into practical and every day-use format for non-specialist audiences. Within this subtask, the principal output was the children's recipe book *Let's Cook Seafood! - Simple Recipes for Kids*²⁴, complemented by recipe cards and by its integration into the VeriFish digital ecosystem. Together, these products were intended to make the nutritional dimension of the VeriFish framework more accessible and actionable, especially for children and families, while also creating potential value for educators, schools, and other intermediaries interested in food literacy and seafood-related education. In contrast to more explanatory or awareness-oriented media products, the cookbook translated project content into behaviour-oriented use, connecting seafood knowledge directly to food preparation and consumption practices.

The cookbook and associated recipe cards were made publicly available through the VeriFish website and were also integrated into the VeriFish web application. Recipes were linked directly to species-specific pages, allowing users to move between practical cooking content and the underlying species and indicator-based information provided through the wider project infrastructure. This is an important feature because it meant the cookbook did not function only as an isolated communication product. It also acted as an entry point into the web app and as a complementary layer within the broader VeriFish ecosystem. In that sense, the cookbook supported not only communication of nutritional themes, but also the wider usability and navigability of other project outputs.

²⁴ <https://verifish.info/verifish-cookbook/>

The cookbook was developed through collaboration between nutrition scientists and designers in order to balance scientific reliability with accessibility and usability. It included 30 recipes organised across different seafood categories, such as lean whitefish, oily fish, and shellfish, and reflected species commonly available across Europe while also encouraging greater diversification of seafood consumption. The recipes were adapted for children, with clear instructions, practical guidance, and attention to safety-related aspects such as the identification of critical steps and the inclusion of allergen information. Each recipe was also accompanied by short contextual content, including species-related facts, which helped extend the educational value of the product beyond the immediate act of cooking. This design approach was appropriate because it made the cookbook more than a collection of recipes. It turned it into an educational media product capable of linking preparation, nutrition, and species awareness in a single format.

Figure 49: Cookbook design and recipe example

Nutritional information was integrated throughout the cookbook and focused on nutrients of particular relevance to seafood, including protein, omega-3 fatty acids, and micronutrients such as iodine, selenium, zinc, vitamin D, and vitamin B12. Values were presented both per 100 grams and as percentages of dietary reference values based on European Food Safety Authority recommendations for children aged 7 to 10 years, using enhanced European food composition data. A glossary was also included to support interpretation by children and adults alike. This is important because it shows that the cookbook was not merely promotional or decorative. It retained a clear educational and indicator-related basis, even while simplifying the presentation for non-specialist users.

The primary audience for the cookbook was children and their families, although the product was also designed with potential use by intermediaries in mind, including schools, educators, and community organisations. Its structure supported both guided and independent use, making it potentially useful in educational, community, and household contexts. At the same time, the evidence available within the reporting period suggests that, while usability was strong by design, documented uptake by intermediaries remained limited. This should be understood in light of the prototype nature of the output and the time constraints of the project rather than as a sign of conceptual weakness. The product clearly had the characteristics of a reusable educational tool, but broader evidence of institutional reuse would require longer-term follow-up beyond the project period.

The cookbook interacted with the VeriFish indicator framework primarily through the nutrition pillar and through its integration into the web app. By embedding simplified nutritional information and connecting recipes to species-specific pages, it created a two-way path of access. Users could approach indicator-based information through cooking and food practice, while also moving from recipes towards more detailed species data and contextual information. In this way, the cookbook complemented other T3.4 outputs, such as factsheets and media products, by providing a practical, behaviour-oriented entry point into the framework. It did not attempt to reproduce the full structure of the environmental or socio-economic pillars within the recipes themselves, and this limitation should be stated clearly. Rather than presenting the entire framework in condensed form, the cookbook functioned as an entry point into the wider logic of VeriFish through the everyday language of food preparation and family consumption.

This output differs from the other media products developed under T3.4 because it translates information into direct action. By embedding knowledge within cooking practices, the cookbook enabled users to engage with VeriFish concepts in a tangible and immediately applicable way. The recipe cards further increased this flexibility by making the content usable in different formats and settings. By linking species to recipes and encouraging preparation and consumption in familiar contexts, the cookbook supported understanding of seafood choices, promoted dietary diversity, and reinforced the connection between knowledge and behaviour. While it primarily reflected the nutrition pillar, it also contributed indirectly to wider sustainability objectives by encouraging diversification of seafood consumption and by increasing awareness of species-level differences. Environmental and socio-economic indicators were not explicitly embedded in the cookbook itself, which means that its role should be understood as complementary rather than comprehensive.

Within the logic of the project, the cookbook contributed to several objectives. It supported the delivery of an accessible media product for awareness and engagement and reinforced the role of the web application as a central point of access by being integrated into that digital environment. It also translated indicator-based information into practical food choices and created a format with potential value for intermediaries such as schools and educators. More broadly, it demonstrated how sustainability- and nutrition-related information can be communicated effectively through everyday-use products rather than through abstract explanatory formats alone. In that respect, the cookbook stands as the main food and nutrition output within T3.4 and as one of the clearest examples of how the VeriFish framework could be translated into daily-life communication contexts.

7.4. Subtask 3.4.5 Social media challenges and storytelling activities

Subtask 3.4.5 included the development of social media challenge-based communication and storytelling activities designed to make the VeriFish project more accessible, more human-centred, and more relatable to audiences that would not necessarily engage with technical descriptions of the indicator framework on their own. Within this subtask, the most relevant actions were the VeriFish Photo Challenge and the VeriFish storytelling campaign based on short videos featuring fishers from Croatia and Hungary. These activities were important because they created communication formats capable of translating the project's broader concerns into concrete, visible, and personal narratives. Instead of presenting the project only through methodological language or formal dissemination outputs, these activities brought

it closer to real people, real practices, and everyday relationships with fish, fisheries, and seafood. In doing so, they helped open alternative entry points into the project for audiences more likely to respond to images, stories, and practical experience than to technical explanations alone.

7.4.1. VeriFish Photo Challenge

The VeriFish Photo Challenge²⁵ was developed as a participatory and visually oriented communication activity and was made publicly available through the project website, where it had its own dedicated page, while also being promoted through the project's social media channels. Its purpose was to encourage interaction with the project in a lighter and more accessible format, using photography as a way to connect users to seafood, fisheries, aquatic environments, and the broader themes of sustainability and awareness. The logic behind the challenge was not simply to increase visibility through a generic social media action, but to create a format that could stimulate engagement, user participation, and a more personal connection with the subject matter of the project. Compared with a technical presentation of the indicator framework, the challenge offered a much simpler and more intuitive route into the wider communication goals of VeriFish. It invited audiences to look, notice, and reflect rather than to interpret indicators directly, and in that sense, it functioned as an awareness-raising bridge between the public and the more structured content developed elsewhere in the project.

Figure 50: VeriFish Photo Challenge Overall Winner and Best in Environmental Sustainability (Author: Lorenzo Ragazzy, Italy)

²⁵ <https://verifish.info/verifish-photo-challenge/>

7.4.2. VeriFish Storytelling campaign

The storytelling campaign had a different role from the more technical communication outputs, but it supported the same overall objective. It used short video testimonies from two Croatian fishers^{26,27} and one Hungarian fisher²⁸, to present fisheries and seafood through personal experience rather than institutional language. This gave the project a more human and grounded tone. Instead of speaking about sustainability only through indicators or technical concepts, the videos showed how fisheries are shaped by everyday realities such as environmental change, adaptation, market pressures, and working life at sea. This made the campaign especially useful as a communication format because it connected VeriFish to the people and contexts the project was trying to support.

These videos were also valuable because they reached audiences that do not always respond well to more technical project communication. While they were accessible to the general public, they were also relevant for sector stakeholders, educators, consumers, and others interested in the practical side of seafood production and sustainability. In this way, the campaign helped shift the focus from the internal structure of the framework to the real-world reasons why clearer and more trustworthy seafood communication is needed. That did not mean oversimplifying the project. It meant presenting its relevance in a format that people could relate to more easily.

Within the broader logic of Task 3.4, the storytelling campaign complemented other media products by adding a more narrative and accessible layer to the communication portfolio. Its purpose was not to replace the app, the factsheets, or the guidelines, but to widen the entry points into the project. The same applies to the Photo Challenge, which encouraged lighter and more participatory engagement. Together, these formats helped balance the more formal and technical outputs of the project with content based on visibility, participation, and personal perspective.

7.5. Influencer's campaigns

7.5.1. Overview and strategic objectives

The influencer engagement campaigns formed a targeted component of the broader VeriFish communication and dissemination strategy and were designed to extend the reach of selected project outputs through trusted external communicators with established niche audiences. Rather than using influencers for generic visibility alone, the campaigns were structured to amplify concrete project assets, translate complex sustainability concepts into accessible formats, and direct users towards active engagement with the project, including the Community of Practice, the web application, and educational media products.

The campaigns were segmented strategically to address different audience groups across the seafood communication landscape. Industry stakeholders and professionals were targeted through content linked to the VeriFish web application, the Community of Practice, and broader policy and communication

²⁶ <https://youtu.be/BJTA-rmRJ6k?si=56iUED5ZYXD7y5II>

²⁷ <https://youtu.be/zay5DJZqMHA?si=FQ0Cd4TvR-3LzTbi>

²⁸ https://youtu.be/7LXpZ_V-WkQ?si=iVDL4Jq_1NDaov7g

discussions. Educators, schools, and younger audiences were targeted through media products with educational value, especially the Overfished! card game. Everyday consumers were approached through practical culinary content designed to connect sustainable seafood choices with familiar cooking behaviour and food-related decision-making.

Specific contractual key performance indicators were established to measure campaign efficacy. For Danielle Leoni, the campaign targets included a total reach above 1,000, total impressions above 2,000, and more than 1,500 video views across all deliverables by 30 April 2026. For Emily De Sousa, campaign success was assessed primarily through LinkedIn engagement and newsletter open- and click-rate performance, reflecting the more professional and educational orientation of her audience.

7.5.2. Campaign design and target audiences

The influencer selection process was based on niche expertise, audience demographics, platform suitability, and alignment with the communication values of VeriFish. Two profiles were used in a complementary way.

Emily De Sousa’s campaigns were divided into two phases. The first, launched in December 2025, focused on industry awareness and thought leadership by introducing VeriFish, reinforcing project credibility, and building on the Euronews coverage produced around the project’s participation in the Catch Welfare Platform context. This campaign relied on a LinkedIn article and two newsletter features, one distributed to consumer subscribers and one to industry subscribers. The second, launched in February 2026, focused on consumer education and product visibility by positioning the *Overfished!* card game as a tool for improving seafood literacy, especially in educational settings. This phase included a short-form video shared through Seaside and Emily’s Instagram and TikTok channels, three Instagram story frames, and a LinkedIn article.

Danielle Leoni’s campaign, launched in April 2026, was designed to bring the VeriFish recipe book to life through chef-led vertical cooking videos. She was asked to produce original content around three selected recipes and to adapt the material to the communication logic of each platform. The recipes highlighted in the campaign were Tuna Dip, Cod Nuggets, and Baked Sardines. The content was framed to connect practical cooking with the broader sustainability and seafood communication goals of VeriFish.

Table 6: Targeting logic summary of the two influencers engaged

Influencer	Niche / expertise	Primary platforms	Main target audience	Main campaign focus
Emily De Sousa	Seafood literacy, marine science, fisheries communication	LinkedIn, custom newsletters	Industry stakeholders, educators, youth-oriented and communication-focused audiences	VeriFish thought leadership, Euronews-related awareness, Community of Practice, web app, educational value of media products
Danielle Leoni	Sustainable culinary arts, chef-led food communication	Instagram, LinkedIn	Consumers, home cooks, food-system professionals	Recipe-led visibility for the VeriFish recipe book and practical communication of sustainable seafood choices

7.5.3. Campaign execution and content strategy

Each influencer was provided with campaign-specific guidelines aligned with the intended communication objective. Emily De Sousa was asked to run two distinct campaigns. The first focused on the Euronews video documentary and directed professional audiences towards the Community of Practice and the web application. The second focused on VeriFish media products, especially the Overfished! card game, and positioned it as an educational tool for schools and younger audiences.

Danielle Leoni was briefed to animate the VeriFish recipe book through original, chef-led short videos filmed in a domestic kitchen environment. The intention was to translate project content into an immediately usable and recognisable everyday format. Platform-adapted captioning was required to ensure that the cooking content remained clearly linked to the sustainability and seafood communication aims of the project rather than being perceived as stand-alone recipe content.

To ensure transparency and communication compliance, all influencers signed dedicated contracts agreed through the project coordinator. These contracts explicitly defined the expected deliverables and campaign KPIs, thereby ensuring that the collaborations remained aligned with the project's dissemination objectives and reporting logic²⁹.

7.5.4. Campaign outputs

Table 7: Summary of the campaign outputs produced through the two influencer collaborations

Campaign period	Influencer	Main focus	Outputs delivered
Dec/25	Emily De Sousa	Industry awareness, project credibility, Euronews-related visibility, direction to CoP and web app	1 LinkedIn article/post, 2 newsletter features (consumer and industry audiences)
January–February 2026	Emily De Sousa	Educational visibility for VeriFish media products, especially Overfished!	1 short-form video shared via Seaside with Emily's Instagram and TikTok, 3 Instagram story frames, 1 LinkedIn article
Apr/26	Danielle Leoni	Consumer-facing culinary activation of the VeriFish recipe book	Chef-led vertical recipe videos for three recipes, distributed primarily through Instagram Reel format and LinkedIn adaptation

7.5.5. Results and impact analysis

The available data indicates that the campaigns performed strongly overall, although with clear differences between influencer profiles and platforms.

Emily De Sousa's LinkedIn-led campaigns produced particularly strong visibility and engagement within niche professional and educational audiences. The December 2025 campaign generated 7,216 impressions and reached 4,681 members, while also producing 64 reactions, 2 comments, 3 reposts, and 16 sends on LinkedIn. The February 2026 campaign performed even more strongly in terms of visibility and interaction, generating 8,269 impressions, reaching 4,944 members, and receiving 52 reactions, 19

²⁹ All influencer collaborations were formalised through dedicated contracts managed by the project coordinator and included KPI and compliance requirements.

comments, 4 reposts, and 8 sends. These results suggest not only stable reach, but also a higher depth of interaction in the second campaign, particularly through the increase in comments.

Emily’s newsletter ecosystem also provided an important distribution layer for the campaign, combining a base of more than 1,200 subscribers with average benchmark rates of 40% open rate and 23% click rate.⁴

The detailed newsletter analytics were reported separately in the campaign documentation and should be referenced in the corresponding performance tables for the December and February editions.

Table 8: Summary of the available LinkedIn campaign metrics for Emily De Sousa

Campaign	Impressions	Members reached	Reactions	Comments	Reposts	Sends on LinkedIn
Dec/25	7,216	4,681	64	2	3	16
Feb/26	8,269	4,944	52	19	4	8

Danielle Leoni’s April 2026 campaign performed strongly on Instagram and more modestly on LinkedIn.

Table 9: Summary of Danielle Leoni’s April 2026 campaign on Instagram

Instagram post	Views	Reach	Likes	Saves	Comments	Shares	Follows
Tuna Dip	3,438	1,83	58	48	3	3	32
Cod Nuggets	3,951	2,704	120	160	8	0	41
Baked Sardines	2,613	1,801	66	64	0	6	31

On LinkedIn, the same campaign produced lower but still measurable performance.

Table 10: Danielle Leoni’s April 2026 campaign on LinkedIn

LinkedIn post	Impressions	Reach	Video views	Watch time	Avg. watch	Reactions	Comments	Reposts	Saves	Profile views
Cod Nuggets	258	149	110	20m 8s	10s	12	2	1	1	2
Baked Sardines	261	167	104	20m 34s	11s	9	0	1	0	0
Tuna Dip	301	181	117	24m 23s	12s	7	0	1		

7.5.6. Visual evidence and Links:

- Emily De Sousa LinkedIn Newsletter (23 Dec 2025): [Building a More Informed Seafood Future](#)
- Emily De Sousa LinkedIn Newsletter (23 Feb 2026): [How VeriFish is Making Seafood Literacy Fun](#)
- Danielle Leoni LinkedIn Reel (15 April 2026): [VeriFish Sustainable Seafood Activity](#)
 - Danielle Leoni [Instagram Reel](#) (15 April 2026)
- Danielle Leoni LinkedIn Reel (18 April 2026): [Codfish Nuggets Recipe](#)
 - Danielle Leoni [Instagram Reel](#) (18 April 2026)

Figure 51: First Post published on LinkedIn - Why Seafood Sustainability Matters: Biology

Figure 52: Graphic of the 2nd Campaign Post - Recipe of the Day: Anchovy Pizza (Romana)

Figure 53: Graphic of the 3rd Campaign Post - Recipe of the Day: Simple Tuna Dip

Figure 54: Graphic of the 4th Campaign Post - Recipe of the Day: Mackerel Patties

Figure 55: Graphic of the 5th Campaign Post - Recipe of the Day: Simple Shrimp Skewers

7.5.7. Conclusions

Emily De Sousa’s campaigns generated strong and consistent reach within a niche professional and educational audience. Both LinkedIn editions achieved high visibility, with more than 7,000 and 8,000 impressions respectively and close to 5,000 members reached. Engagement was also positive, particularly in the February edition, where the increase in comments suggested stronger audience interaction. Overall, the results show a solid communication presence in the seafood literacy and sustainability space.

Danielle Leoni’s campaign performed best on Instagram, where the recipe reels generated clear organic traction and strong engagement. The fact that saves exceeded likes suggests that users found the content useful and worth revisiting, which is especially relevant for recipe-based communication. The conversion into followers was also strong for a campaign based on only three posts. On LinkedIn, results were more modest, but still showed meaningful engagement through video views, watch time, reactions, reposts, and link clicks.

The main lesson is that performance depends strongly on the fit between content, platform, and audience. Emily De Sousa’s work shows that seafood literacy and thought-leadership content can perform well when shared through a trusted professional profile, while Danielle Leoni’s results show that culinary storytelling works particularly well in consumer-facing visual platforms. A related lesson is that the same asset does not perform equally across all channels. Danielle Leoni’s recipe videos worked well on Instagram but required stronger adaptation for LinkedIn. Overall, the influencer campaigns showed that targeted third-party communication can help make specialised project outputs more visible, accessible, and relevant to audiences beyond the project’s own channels.

7.6. Indicator framework implementation in different contexts

The VeriFish indicator framework was applied across several media products and communication formats, with the level of detail adjusted to the intended audience and use context. In all cases, the aim was to

preserve the core principle of verifiable, indicator-based information while making it usable for non-specialist audiences.

In factsheets and the web application, the framework was translated into structured, species-specific information designed for clarity, comparability, and ease of use. In educational products such as posters, games, and school-oriented materials, it was simplified further to focus on key concepts and support awareness, curiosity, and understanding. In food-related outputs, especially the cookbook, the framework was expressed mainly through the nutrition pillar and linked to species-level information through the app, connecting project content to everyday food choices. In storytelling and citizen-facing campaigns, the framework was translated into higher-level messages and narratives that prioritised accessibility and engagement while still respecting the principle of verifiability.

Across all formats, the main challenge was balancing accessibility with complexity. Full representation of the framework was not always possible or useful for non-specialist audiences, so communication relied on selection, simplification, and visualisation. Even so, the simplified outputs remained aligned with the underlying framework and, where possible, linked back to more detailed information through the VeriFish web application. In this way, the project showed that the framework could be communicated in accessible forms without losing its core logic.

7.7. Main lessons from T3.4

The VeriFish indicator framework was translated into a range of media products and communication formats, with the level of detail adapted to the intended audience and use context. In all cases, the aim was to preserve the principle of verifiable, indicator-based information while making it usable for non-specialist audiences.

In factsheets and the web application, the framework was presented as clear, structured species-level information. In educational materials such as posters, games, and school-oriented products, it was simplified to focus on core concepts and support awareness and understanding. In food-related products, especially the cookbook, it was mainly expressed through the nutrition pillar and linked back to species-level data through the app. In storytelling and citizen-facing campaigns, it was translated into higher-level messages and narratives that prioritised accessibility and engagement. Across all of these formats, complexity was reduced, but the principle of verifiability was maintained and, where possible, linked back to more detailed information.

8. Task 3.5 – Events & VeriFish conference

Task 3.5 supported the dissemination and stakeholder engagement strategy of VeriFish through a combination of external event participation and project-organised activities. Its purpose was to increase visibility, present project results in relevant professional and institutional settings, create opportunities for stakeholder dialogue, and support feedback and validation around key outputs. In a project such as VeriFish, events were particularly useful because they complemented digital communication with direct

discussion and exchange around the framework, the web app, the media products, and the wider communication approach.

External events allowed VeriFish to position itself within ongoing discussions in the seafood, fisheries, aquaculture, sustainability, policy, and research fields. Their value lay mainly in reaching relevant audiences, strengthening visibility, and connecting the project with sector, advisory, scientific, and policy-related communities. The most useful events were those where the project could present concrete outputs and create opportunities for interaction, such as sector fairs, scientific conferences, advisory meetings, and clustering or policy-related events.

The main project-organised milestone under this task was the VeriFish final conference, held in Brussels from 10 to 12 March 2026. As described in detail in Deliverable *D3.9: VeriFish dissemination events roadmap*, the event combined three complementary elements: a CEN Workshop Agreement session, a public final event, and a consortium follow-up meeting. This structure allowed the project not only to present results, but also to discuss them with stakeholders and use the feedback to support final refinements of the app, guidelines, and related outputs. The public event itself was organised around the environmental, nutritional, and socio-economic dimensions of the VeriFish framework and included a validation workshop focused on the web app, the guidelines, and the media products.

Stakeholder participation in events was strongest among research and scientific communities, seafood-sector actors, and advisory or policy-related audiences. These groups were particularly relevant because they could assess the framework, app, and communication products in practical and informed terms. Broader citizen and educational audiences were less visible in formal event settings and were reached more effectively through media products, campaigns, and website-based communication.

Overall, Task 3.5 showed that events were most effective when they combined visibility with interaction. Their strongest value came not from the number of appearances, but from the relevance of the audience, the fit between the event and the project outputs, and the opportunities created for discussion, validation, and follow-up. A fuller account of the event strategy, final conference, and event participation record is provided in *Deliverable D3.9: VeriFish dissemination events roadmap*.

9. Stakeholder engagement results across WP3

Across WP3, stakeholder engagement went beyond visibility and was understood as a combination of awareness, participation, feedback, testing, validation, reuse, and, in some cases, stakeholder-led amplification of project outputs. This approach was necessary because VeriFish did not aim only to communicate results, but also to assess whether its tools and materials were understandable, relevant, and usable for different audiences.

The strongest engagement was achieved among research and scientific communities, seafood-sector stakeholders, and advisory or policy-related actors. These groups were reached mainly through the app, factsheets, scientific dissemination, events, the Community of Practice, and targeted stakeholder activities. Their participation was often active, especially in settings where the project created

opportunities for exchange and validation, such as the final event, the Catch Welfare Platform working lunch, and app-related feedback moments. Seafood producers, fisheries organisations, and aquaculture actors were especially important because they are close to the practical settings where seafood sustainability communication is applied, while policy, advisory, and standards-related actors were strategically relevant for credibility and links to guidance-oriented work.

Educators, children, families, and the wider public were reached mainly through educational and public-facing outputs such as the cookbook, the Overfished! card game, the calendar, the puzzle, the fishing methods poster, storytelling materials, the website, and social media campaigns. Their engagement was generally lighter and less tied to technical validation, but it was important for accessibility, awareness, and broader public understanding. Consumer organisations and associations were also relevant, mainly as multipliers and users of communication-oriented outputs rather than as direct contributors to technical testing.

Overall, WP3 showed a clear difference between visibility and deeper engagement. The broadest audiences were reached through the website, social media, campaigns, and media products, while the most substantial two-way exchange took place where stakeholders were given something concrete to test, request, discuss, or validate. The main lesson is that engagement works best when the format matches the audience and when communication is linked to practical tools, structured feedback opportunities, and clear entry points into the project's results.

10. Performance assessment of communication and dissemination

10.1. KPI framework

The KPI framework for WP3 was based on the indicators defined in the Grant Agreement and covered both the core communication channels and the specific tools and campaigns planned under the work package. This approach was important because WP3 was designed as a mixed communication and stakeholder-engagement package, combining website and social media outreach with editorial content, videos, events, media products, and validation-oriented activities. The assessment therefore followed the project-specific targets originally set for these actions rather than relying only on general communication metrics.

At the more general communication level, the Grant Agreement defined KPIs for the public website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and participation in third-party events. These were intended to measure the continuity and visibility of the project's main dissemination infrastructure. In parallel, more specific KPIs were attached to the dynamic factsheets, the web app, awareness-raising videos, influencer campaigns, the Eurofish Magazine articles, the Instagram video challenge, storytelling sessions, promotion of media products, the Community of Practice, and stakeholder workshops. Together, these indicators provided the reference structure against which WP3 performance was assessed.

Table 11: KPI framework for WP3 based on the Grant Agreement

Tool / activity	Function	KPI in Grant Agreement
Project public website	SEO-driven website showcasing project assets, outputs, and events, with analytics tracked monthly	>1k sessions/month by M12; >3k sessions/month by M24
Social media	Presence and engagement across social platforms to build the project's network and reach the identified stakeholder categories	500 followers by M12; 1000 by M24
Newsletters	Reader-friendly email updates on project activities and results	4 by M12; 12 by M24
Press releases	Dissemination of newsworthy project results or events to relevant media and publishers	2 by M12; 5 by M24
Third-party events	Dissemination of VeriFish results and activities at external events targeting main stakeholder groups	20 events attended by project partners
VeriFish dynamic factsheets	Dynamic factsheets on the VeriFish web app as an extension to the GRSF semantic knowledge base	10 factsheets; 7 fisheries; 3 aquaculture
Distribution of web app	Dissemination of the VeriFish web application across target stakeholders	>1k visits by M6; >3k visits by M36
VeriFish awareness-raising videos	Short pitch-style videos and interviews distributed through VeriFish social media channels	30
Influencer videos	Videos or podcasts produced by external influencers on nutrition, sustainability, and biodiversity aspects	5 influencers engaged
Eurofish Magazine	Publication of articles in Eurofish Magazine on how consumers can "choose fish" in different market segments	3500 impressions on the website
Instagram video challenge	Video challenge engaging chefs, fishers, nutritionists, students, or young fishers on sustainable seafood communication	20
Storytelling sessions	Short seafood-related stories distributed via website, social media, newsletters, and partner networks	3 stories created
Promotion of VeriFish media products	Engagement with educational channels, associations, and NGOs to promote the web app and media products	100 entities engaged; 20 countries covered
PPC social media	Paid social media campaigns to broaden stakeholder reach and increase followers	20
Community of Practice	Build and animate an engaged stakeholder community to co-design, assess, validate, and promote outputs	3000 overall community members database; 800 CoP members on LinkedIn group; 100 actors listed and identified in CoP database; 20 consumer networks and associations in 10 countries
Requirement-gathering workshops	Online design and requirements workshops with fisheries, aquaculture, retailers, and consumers	2 × 4 participants per stakeholder category
Community validation workshops	On-site workshops for validation of indicators and guidelines	20 average participants per workshop

10.2. Quantitative results

The quantitative results show that WP3 delivered a broad and active dissemination portfolio that exceeded several of its initial communication targets. The strongest results were achieved where communication was linked to concrete outputs, such as the web app, the cookbook, the media products, the final event, the card game, and the video and influencer campaigns. Website traffic, LinkedIn visibility, newsletter continuity, and the level of external requests for selected products all point to a communication strategy that moved beyond static project visibility and generated repeated external interaction.

Several activities exceeded expectations. The total number of social media followers surpassed the final target of 1,000. Website sessions more than doubled the target of 3,000 by month 24. The project also exceeded the expected number of Eurofish Magazine articles and video outputs, and the final communication portfolio became broader and more diversified than would normally be expected from a project of this type. The development and public rollout of educational and practical media products, combined with influencer-led activity and app-linked dissemination, gave WP3 a wider communicative footprint than a narrower interpretation of the plan would have produced.

Table 12: Summary of the main quantitative results

Area	Indicator	Result
Website	Total users	4,994
Website	New users	4,984
Website	Sessions	7,29
Website	Page views	10,29
Website	Average session duration	131.3 seconds
Website	Views per session	01.41
Website	Form starts	419
Website	Form submissions	62
Website	Video starts on website	107
Website	Video progress events	306
Social media	Total followers across platforms	1,064
LinkedIn	Followers	838
Instagram	Followers	132
X	Followers	42
Facebook	Followers	30
Bluesky	Followers	22
LinkedIn	Posts published	113
LinkedIn	Impressions	39,992
LinkedIn	Clicks	3,458
LinkedIn	Likes	1,318
LinkedIn	Comments	16
LinkedIn	Reposts	179
LinkedIn	Average engagement rate	11.3%
LinkedIn	Average click-through rate	7.2%
Newsletter	Subscribers	84
Newsletter	Newsletters published by 13/04/2026	12
Newsletter	Final newsletter prepared	1

Eurofish Magazine	Published articles	7
Videos / YouTube	Videos published	23
Videos / YouTube	Additional videos in final production	2
Videos / YouTube	Total views	600
Videos / YouTube	Watch time	8.0 hours
Videos / YouTube	Impressions	4,701
Videos / YouTube	Subscribers gained	20
Videos / YouTube	Overall click-through rate	3.06%
Community of Practice	Active members	207
App uptake	Direct requests for web app	42
Media product uptake	Direct requests for Overfished! and related media products	69
Card game uptake	Online requests processed	68
External events	Final event duration	3 days

10.3. Qualitative results

The strongest qualitative results of WP3 were seen in stakeholder interest, usability of outputs, reuse potential, and the ability of communication formats to make the VeriFish framework easier to understand. Stakeholder feedback consistently showed that the most positively received outputs were those that translated complex concepts into practical and recognisable formats, especially the web app, factsheets, cookbook, educational media products, videos, and validation-oriented events.

Interest in these outputs was visible not only through traffic and impressions, but also through direct requests, targeted feedback, event participation, and product uptake. Requests for the web app and media products came from a wide range of organisations, showing that the project's outputs were seen as relevant beyond the consortium itself. The Community of Practice, the Catch Welfare Platform working lunch, and the final event also generated useful feedback that helped improve the app and other outputs.

Overall, WP3 supported understanding of the indicator framework by translating it into different formats for different audiences. The app and factsheets provided structured access to the framework, while the cookbook, media products, videos, and storytelling materials made selected dimensions more accessible in everyday, educational, and public-facing contexts. Together, these outputs created a layered communication ecosystem that made the framework more approachable without losing its core logic.

Table 13: Main qualitative outputs

Qualitative dimension	Main result
Stakeholder feedback	Strongest where outputs could be tested directly, especially app and validation sessions
Reuse potential	High for educational media products, cookbook, card game, factsheets, and app
External interest	Demonstrated through direct requests from institutions, NGOs, industry, research, and schools
Clarity of outputs	Improved over time through redesign, layered presentation, and stakeholder input
Framework understanding	Strengthened through segmentation into app, factsheets, videos, media products, and practical tools

10.4. Deviations from initial planning

The implementation of WP3 was broadly aligned with the original intent of the Description of Action and the logic of D3.1, but several activities evolved in scale, emphasis, or format as the project progressed. In general, these deviations were positive and reflected adaptation to actual stakeholder response, output maturity, and communication opportunity rather than failure to deliver.

Some activities were adapted over time. The website evolved from a more introductory project page into a results-oriented dissemination platform. The app underwent major technical and user-interface refinement. The Community of Practice became more active in the later phases of the project, especially once concrete outputs such as the app and card game were available. Likewise, communication around the project became more effective as more tangible outputs could be promoted, rather than only project concepts.

Table 14: Overall implementation against initial planning

Area	Initial intent	Actual implementation
Website	Public project hub	Evolved into results-oriented dissemination platform
Social media	Multi-channel visibility	Achieved, with LinkedIn clearly dominant
Newsletters	At least bi-monthly communication	12 newsletters delivered, plus final one prepared
Editorial output	Minimum 5 articles	7 articles published
Video output	Short video trailer series	Expanded to 23 published videos plus 2 in final production
Stakeholder engagement	Community-building and validation	Achieved, especially through CoP, app requests, and validation workshops
Public educational tools	Planned media products	Delivered as a diversified portfolio with measurable external demand

10.5. Support to WP2 outputs

WP3 played a central role in translating WP2's technical outputs into usable and communicable formats. The indicator framework, scoring logic, knowledge base, and guidance-related content developed in WP2 would have remained inaccessible to most external audiences without the communication and engagement work carried out under WP3.

The app was the clearest example of this translation. It acted as the operational front end through which the Knowledge Base and the framework became intelligible to end users. The factsheets provided a structured and layered way to access the same logic at species level. The videos, website pages, events, and communication materials made the three pillars easier to explain. The cookbook and media products translated parts of the framework, especially the nutrition and species-awareness dimensions, into practical everyday formats. The final result was that WP2's technical architecture was not only preserved but made visible and usable.

Table 15: Summary of the support of WP3 to WP2

WP2 output	WP3 translation format
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Indicator framework	App, factsheets, website pages, videos, event sessions
Scoring logic	App presentation, factsheet structure, explanatory communication
Knowledge Base	App front end, searchable user interface, simplified access pathways
Guidelines-related content	Events, validation workshops, website content, stakeholder discussion

10.6. Support to WP4 recommendations and standardisation-related work

WP3 also supported WP4 by preparing the ground for recommendations, consensus-building, and stakeholder-facing guidance. Through communication, stakeholder engagement, and event-based interaction, WP3 helped expose project outputs to the types of users and expert communities whose feedback was relevant for later recommendation and standardisation-oriented work.

This support was particularly visible in the final event, the CEN Workshop Agreement process, the Community of Practice, and the wider event portfolio. WP3 created the channels through which discussions around communication practices, framework usability, stakeholder expectations, and practical guidance could emerge. It also helped gather reactions from advisory actors, standards-related stakeholders, and professional users whose perspectives could feed into more formal recommendation outputs.

The contribution of WP3 to WP4 therefore lay in creating the engagement conditions for later consensus-oriented work. It helped ensure that recommendation-related outputs were not developed in isolation, but were informed by exposure, discussion, validation, and stakeholder dialogue.

11. Conclusions and recommendations

11.1. Main conclusions

WP3 made a substantial contribution to the visibility, accessibility, and practical communication of VeriFish throughout the project period. Its main added value was not simply that it increased the public presence of the project, but that it translated complex technical and conceptual outputs into formats that could be understood and used by a wider range of stakeholders. Through the combination of the website, social media, newsletters, editorial content, videos, events, the web application, factsheets, and educational media products, WP3 helped turn VeriFish from a technical framework into a communication ecosystem with multiple access points for different audiences. In this respect, the work package contributed positively to all three of its main functions: making the project visible, making its outputs more understandable, and creating opportunities for stakeholder engagement around them.

Among the strongest outputs were the VeriFish web application, the factsheets, the cookbook, the educational media products, the video series, and the stakeholder-facing event activities. These outputs were particularly valuable because they moved beyond abstract explanation and offered users something more concrete to explore, test, request, use, or discuss. The app and factsheets provided the clearest digital implementation of the framework, while the cookbook, card game, calendar, puzzle, and poster made selected dimensions of the project more approachable in everyday and educational contexts. The final event, the Community of Practice, and the validation-oriented activities added a further layer of value by allowing stakeholders to respond to the outputs rather than only receive them. In terms of channels, the website and LinkedIn were the strongest and most strategically relevant platforms, while newsletters, Eurofish Magazine articles, videos, and event-based dissemination played important complementary roles in reinforcing continuity, professional credibility, and stakeholder contact.

The project also generated solid evidence that the indicator framework can be communicated in accessible ways when appropriate formats are used. This is visible in several layers of the WP3 portfolio. The web app and factsheets showed that multidimensional indicator-based information can be organised in a user-friendly and navigable format. The videos, storytelling materials, and influencer campaigns demonstrated that key ideas can be translated into short, recognisable, and audience-appropriate content. The cookbook and educational media products showed that selected dimensions of the framework, especially nutrition, species awareness, fishing methods, and responsible seafood choices, can be embedded into practical and every day-use materials. Together, these outputs suggest that the framework is not limited to expert communication and can support broader forms of public and stakeholder understanding when it is mediated through well-designed tools and products.

11.2. Recommendations for future projects

One of the clearest recommendations emerging from WP3 is the importance of stakeholder segmentation from the start of the communication process. Different audiences respond to different levels of complexity, different formats, and different channels, and this should be planned deliberately rather than adjusted only later in implementation. Future projects would benefit from defining more explicit

stakeholder pathways at an early stage, distinguishing more clearly between audiences to be informed, audiences to be engaged in dialogue, and audiences to be involved in testing, validation, or reuse.

A second recommendation concerns the timing of co-design and feedback. The experience of VeriFish suggests that co-design and stakeholder validation are especially valuable when they take place early enough to influence outputs and then recur again at later stages when more concrete tools and materials are available. Future projects should therefore build in more than one moment of structured feedback, combining early conceptual co-design with later-stage testing of actual products and tools. This would strengthen both output relevance and the evidence base for stakeholder-centred refinement.

A third recommendation relates to the integration of apps, content, and communication formats. One of the strengths of VeriFish was that the app, factsheets, website, recipes, videos, and media products did not remain entirely separate, but were linked to one another through shared pathways. Future projects should continue to develop this type of integration, ensuring that digital tools are connected to practical content and that user journeys do not end with a single resource but instead lead towards deeper exploration where relevant. This is particularly important for projects trying to communicate structured information without overwhelming users.

The use of factsheets and educational materials should also be considered a strong practice worth continuing. Factsheets are particularly useful because they provide layered access to complex information and can support both quick orientation and deeper consultation. Educational materials, meanwhile, can extend project relevance beyond professional circles and open entry points for schools, families, and wider public audiences. Future projects should therefore consider from the outset how more formal outputs can be complemented by simpler and more reusable materials adapted to educational and citizen-facing contexts.

Video and storytelling formats also proved valuable and should remain part of future communication portfolios. Their greatest strength lies in making abstract or technical subjects more human, more memorable, and more adaptable across channels. The main lesson is not that all projects need large volumes of video content, but that short explainers, expert voices, and story-based formats can help unlock understanding where written technical explanation alone would not be sufficient. Future work should continue to match video style and length more carefully to the expectations of each platform.

With regard to events, the main recommendation is to prioritise quality and fit over volume. The strongest outcomes came from events where the project had a clear role, a relevant audience, and something concrete to present or validate. Future projects should therefore treat events as strategic multipliers linked to outputs, follow-up communication, and stakeholder dialogue rather than as stand-alone dissemination obligations. Hybrid structures that combine public presentation with validation and internal follow-up may be particularly useful in this regard.

A further recommendation concerns KPI tracking. Communication and engagement metrics should be structured from the beginning of the project in a way that distinguishes clearly between output, reach, and engagement. This makes interpretation stronger and reduces the risk of relying on visibility metrics alone. Future projects would benefit from more systematic baseline setting, more regular collection of

comparable data, and earlier definition of how requests, reuse, feedback, and validation will be tracked across different channels and products.

Finally, projects with strong public-facing ambitions should think about post-project sustainability from the beginning rather than only at the end. Digital tools, websites, educational materials, and downloadable products are most valuable when they remain available and navigable beyond the formal project duration. Future initiatives should therefore consider early on what can realistically be maintained, updated, or handed over, and how this can be communicated to potential users in a clear and transparent way.

12. Annexes

12.1. Annex 1. List of communication materials produced

The table below provides an overview of the main communication and dissemination materials produced under WP3. It is intended as a consolidated reference list covering the principal categories of assets developed and used throughout the project.

Table 16: Overview of the main communication and dissemination materials produced under WP3

Category	Material / output	Description / purpose
Branding assets	VeriFish visual identity	Project logo, visual style, branded templates, and core design system used across communication channels and deliverables
Branding assets	Event banners and promotional visuals	Visual materials developed for the kick-off meeting, final event, workshops, newsletters, campaigns, and other dissemination actions
Branding assets	PPC and campaign visuals	Digital visuals prepared for targeted promotion and online dissemination campaigns
Branding assets	Business cards	Printed branded cards used in conferences, fairs, meetings, and stakeholder networking
Website pages	Homepage	Main public entry point to the project and its results
Website pages	About Us page	Overview of project identity, consortium, and objectives
Website pages	News and Events page	Updates on project developments, event participation, and announcements
Website pages	VeriFish web app page	Public-facing information and access point for the digital application
Website pages	VeriFish media product page	Overview and access to public-facing media products
Website pages	VeriFish cookbook page	Dedicated page for the recipe book and related food content
Website pages	Overfished! card game page	Dedicated page for the educational card game and request/download access
Website pages	Interactive Seafood Insights page	Public-facing content linked to app-based or digital species information
Website pages	VeriFish CEN Workshop Agreement page	Information related to the CWA process and related outputs
Website pages	Final event page	Event information, registration, and public-facing dissemination for the final conference
Social media campaigns	General project awareness campaign	Ongoing campaign to introduce VeriFish, its goals, and its outputs across social media channels
Social media campaigns	Fish species and pillar-based campaigns	Content focused on species information and the environmental, nutritional, and socio-economic pillars
Social media campaigns	Output launch campaigns	Promotion of the app, cookbook, card game, calendar, puzzle, factsheets, videos, and other public-facing resources
Social media campaigns	Event promotion campaigns	Communication linked to conferences, workshops, the final event, and external dissemination opportunities
Social media campaigns	Storytelling campaign	Fisher and stakeholder stories used to humanise project themes and connect them to real-life contexts
Social media campaigns	VeriFish Photo Challenge	Participatory campaign inviting users to submit photos and captions related to sustainable seafood

Social media campaigns	Influencer campaigns	Campaigns led by Emily De Sousa and Danielle Leoni to promote seafood literacy, educational tools, and recipe-based outputs
Newsletters	VeriFish newsletters	Twelve newsletters published between October 2024 and April 2026, plus one final newsletter prepared at project closure
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: VeriFish kick-off meeting press release	Early editorial introduction of the project and launch visibility
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: VeriFish introduction	Introductory article presenting the project to professional audiences
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: VeriFish Indicator Framework	Editorial presentation of the framework and its relevance
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: Latest milestones from VeriFish	Progress-focused article highlighting project developments
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: VeriFish Photo Challenge	Article linked to campaign visibility and public-facing engagement
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: Catch Welfare Conference and VeriFish working lunch	Article linking project participation to wider sector debates
Articles	Eurofish Magazine article: Seafood Sustainability is not a joke	Editorial piece reinforcing project visibility and communication positioning
Videos	VeriFish trailer and short video series	Core audiovisual communication series used to explain project themes and outputs
Videos	2 Questions, 6 Perspectives	Expert interview campaign on seafood sustainability and the role of VeriFish
Videos	Building the VeriFish Knowledge Base	Technical explainer on the project's knowledge base and data logic
Videos	External Advisory Board Voices	Video series featuring EAB members and their perspectives
Videos	Voices Behind the Indicators	Interview series recorded during the Catch Welfare Platform context
Videos	A VeriFish Story	Storytelling videos featuring fishers and real-life fisheries perspectives
Videos	Indicator framework explainer videos	Videos focused on the three pillars and related themes such as catch welfare and public data
Videos	Web app demonstration videos	Videos showing the functionality and use of the VeriFish application
Posters	Fishing Methods at a Glance	Educational poster explaining common fishing gears, terminology, and related species
Posters	VeriFish promotional posters	Event and campaign posters used for dissemination and outreach
Factsheets	VeriFish species factsheets	Core species-based information sheets integrating biological, environmental, nutritional, and socio-economic information
Factsheets	Light factsheets	Concise user-facing factsheet view designed for quick consultation
Factsheets	Full factsheets	Expanded detailed view containing the broader multidimensional information linked to the framework
Educational materials	Overfished! card game	Educational and gamified media product designed for children, families, schools, and wider outreach
Educational materials	VeriFish puzzle	Species-recognition and marine biodiversity learning resource
Educational materials	VeriFish puzzle poster version	Poster-based version of the puzzle for visual learning and display

Educational materials	Seasonal seafood calendar	Twelve-month educational calendar linking species, sustainability, nutrition, and recipes
Educational materials	Children and citizens media products suite	Broader set of public-facing and white-label educational materials
Recipe book and related products	Let's Cook Seafood! – Simple Recipes for Kids	Main cookbook developed under WP3 to communicate seafood nutrition and practical food use
Recipe book and related products	Recipe cards	Standalone and reusable recipe formats linked to species and food literacy
Recipe book and related products	App-linked recipe integration	Integration of recipes into species pages and the wider VeriFish digital ecosystem

A shorter inventory by quantity is provided below.

Table 17: Shorter Inventory of assets produced by VeriFish

Material type	Quantity / status
Newsletters published	12
Final newsletter prepared	1
Eurofish Magazine articles published	7
Videos published	23
Videos in final production	2
Core social media platforms used	5
Community of Practice members	207
Web app direct requests	42
Media product direct requests	69
Overfished! card game requests processed	68

12.2. Annex 2. Dissemination KPI tables

The tables below consolidate the main dissemination and stakeholder engagement metrics recorded across WP3. They are grouped by channel, campaign, event, and participation logic in order to distinguish visibility, production, and engagement more clearly.

Table 18: Consolidated dissemination KPI tables for WP3, covering channel performance, campaign-level results, event-related activity, participation and uptake indicators, and summary comparison against selected communication targets.

Table A. Channel metrics			
Channel / asset	Metric	Result	Notes
Website	Total users	4,994	Period covered by comparable analytics: August 2025 to April 2026
Website	New users	4,984	Strong acquisition of first-time visitors
Website	Sessions	7,29	Exceeded final communication target
Website	Page views	10,29	Includes output-specific and event-related pages
Website	Views per session	01.41	Indicates multi-page exploration in part of the audience
Website	Average session duration	131.3 seconds	Approx. 2 min 11 sec
Website	Form starts	419	Indicates active user interaction
Website	Form submissions	62	Includes requests and contact-type conversions
Website	Video starts	107	Website-embedded audiovisual interaction
Website	Video progress events	306	Indicates continued viewing beyond initial play
LinkedIn	Followers	838	Strongest social platform
LinkedIn	Posts published	113	April 2025 to April 2026
LinkedIn	Impressions	39,992	Post-level performance dataset
LinkedIn	Clicks	3,458	High relative click activity
LinkedIn	Likes	1,318	Reactions across post portfolio
LinkedIn	Comments	16	Lower volume but relevant for professional content
LinkedIn	Reposts	179	Important multiplier effect
LinkedIn	Average engagement rate	11.3%	Post-level average
LinkedIn	Average click-through rate	7.2%	Post-level average
LinkedIn page	Page views	860	April 2025 to April 2026
LinkedIn page	Unique visitors	449	Page-level audience metric
Instagram	Followers	132	Secondary but relevant visual platform
X	Followers	42	Supporting visibility channel
Facebook	Followers	30	Supporting visibility channel
Bluesky	Followers	22	Supporting visibility channel
Total social media	Followers across platforms	1,064	Exceeded final target of 1,000
Newsletter	Subscribers	84	Project mailing list
Newsletter	Newsletters published	12	October 2024 to April 2026
YouTube / video channel	Published videos	23	Plus 2 in final production
YouTube / video channel	Total views	600	Niche but meaningful performance
YouTube / video channel	Watch time	8.0 hours	Aggregate channel watch time

YouTube / video channel	Impressions	4,701	Visibility of video catalogue
YouTube / video channel	Subscribers gained	20	Net new audience through video channel
YouTube / video channel	Click-through rate	3.06%	Channel-level CTR
Campaign / activity	Metric	Result	Notes
VeriFish Photo Challenge	Entries received	15+	Students, seafood professionals, and citizens
Emily De Sousa campaign, Dec 2025	LinkedIn impressions	7,216	Professional and thought-leadership campaign
Emily De Sousa campaign, Dec 2025	Members reached	4,681	Strong targeted reach
Emily De Sousa campaign, Dec 2025	Reactions	64	
Emily De Sousa campaign, Dec 2025	Comments	2	
Emily De Sousa campaign, Dec 2025	Reposts	3	
Emily De Sousa campaign, Dec 2025	Sends	16	
Emily De Sousa campaign, Feb 2026	LinkedIn impressions	8,269	Educational/media products focus
Emily De Sousa campaign, Feb 2026	Members reached	4,944	Strong targeted reach
Emily De Sousa campaign, Feb 2026	Reactions	52	
Emily De Sousa campaign, Feb 2026	Comments	19	Higher depth of interaction
Emily De Sousa campaign, Feb 2026	Reposts	4	
Emily De Sousa campaign, Feb 2026	Sends	8	
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Total views	10,002	Three recipe reels
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Total reach	6,335	Strong organic traction
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Likes	244	
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Saves	272	Strong usefulness signal
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Comments	11	
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Shares	9	
Danielle Leoni Instagram campaign	Follows	104	Strong follower conversion for small campaign
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Impressions	820	Same recipe campaign adapted to LinkedIn

Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Reach	497	
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Video views	331	
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Watch time	65m 5s	
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Reactions	28	
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Comments	2	
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Reposts	3	
Danielle Leoni LinkedIn campaign	Link clicks	6	
Event / event type	Metric	Result	Notes
VeriFish final event	Duration	3 days	10–12 March 2026, Brussels
VeriFish final event	Main components	3	CWA workshop, public final event, consortium meeting
Final public event	Main plenary pillars	3	Environmental, nutritional, socio-economic
Final public event	Validation workshop tracks	3	Web app, guidelines, media outputs
Catch Welfare Platform working lunch	Selected participants	26	Producers, associations, researchers, technology actors
External events strategy	Main function types	5	Awareness, scientific dissemination, stakeholder engagement, policy dialogue, education
Consortium external participation	Coverage	Project period	Multiple fairs, conferences, workshops, policy and clustering events
Table D. Participation metrics			
Participation area	Metric	Result	Notes
Community of Practice	Active members	207	Final reporting point
Community of Practice	Recorded individuals	100	Within total membership
Community of Practice	Male individuals	60	Recorded individual members
Community of Practice	Female individuals	40	Recorded individual members
App uptake	Direct requests for access	42	January to end of April 2026
Media product uptake	Direct requests	69	Includes Overfished! and related products
Overfished! card game	Requests processed	68	By 24 April 2026
Educational product reach	Countries represented in requests	Europe + international	Broad geographic spread
Influencer campaign audience base	Emily newsletter subscribers	1,200+	Stated audience base
Influencer campaign audience base	Emily LinkedIn followers	10,000+	Stated audience base

Influencer campaign audience base	Danielle / Seaside TikTok	21,000+	Stated audience base
Influencer campaign audience base	Danielle / Seaside Instagram	15,000+	Stated audience base
Table E. KPI summary against targets			
KPI area	Target	Achieved result	Status
Website sessions	>3,000 by M24	7,29	Exceeded
Social media followers	1,000 by M24	1,064	Exceeded
Newsletters	12 by M24	12 published	Achieved
Eurofish Magazine articles	At least 5	7	Exceeded
Video outputs	4 short trailers originally envisaged	23 published + 2 in final production	Exceeded
Community-building / stakeholder activation	Qualitative and output-based	207 CoP members; app and media requests documented	Strong delivery

12.3. Annex 3. Event participation overview

The table below provides an overview of the main internal and external events relevant to WP3 dissemination and stakeholder engagement. It includes the project-organised final event sequence as well as the most strategically relevant external participations recorded during the project period. The purpose of the table is to show the range of event contexts used by VeriFish, the audiences reached, and the relevance of each event for communication, validation, networking, and dissemination.

Table 19: Overview of the main internal and external events relevant to WP3 dissemination and stakeholder engagement

Date	Event	Type	Main audience	Main purpose	Estimated reach / profile	Relevance for VeriFish
10–12 March 2026	VeriFish Final Event, Brussels	Internal / project-organised	Consortium, researchers, advisory actors, policy-related stakeholders, certification bodies, NGOs, sector actors	Final dissemination, validation, stakeholder dialogue, follow-up for deliverables	High relevance, mixed expert and stakeholder audience across 3 days	Flagship event under T3.5; strongest project-organised dissemination and validation milestone

10/Mar/26	VeriFish CWA Workshop	Internal / project-organised	Consortium, standards-related actors, advisory stakeholders, selected experts	Discussion and consolidation of CWA text, dissemination and follow-up planning	Focused expert audience	Important for recommendation-oriented outputs and consensus-building
11/Mar/26	VeriFish Public Final Event	Internal / project-organised	External stakeholders, project partners, policy, NGO, advisory, research, certification and sector actors	Present project results, discuss three pillars, validate app, guidelines, and media outputs	Broadest attendance of the final event sequence	Core public-facing dissemination moment of the project
12/Mar/26	VeriFish Consortium Meeting	Internal / project-organised	Consortium and selected external experts	Follow-up on feedback, deliverables, exploitation planning	Working-level internal audience	Critical for converting event outcomes into final project outputs
Sept/24	Eurofish Conference on Circular Economy in Seafood, Madrid	External	Seafood stakeholders, conference participants, sector professionals	Awareness raising, professional dissemination	Specialist professional audience	Early visibility opportunity in a relevant seafood policy and sustainability context
Sept/24	Tromsø Seafood Festival, Tromsø	External	Citizens, festival audiences, seafood-interested publics	Public engagement, broader visibility	Public-facing mixed audience	Useful for lighter-touch public-facing awareness
2024	METROFOOD-EPI Stakeholder Workshop / Open Event, Rome	External	Stakeholders in food systems, research and innovation actors	Stakeholder engagement, project positioning	Specialist workshop audience	Relevant for networking and alignment with adjacent initiatives
2024	AQUA 2024, Copenhagen	External	Aquaculture professionals, researchers, sector organisations	Exhibition, networking, dissemination	Large sector event	Important for professional visibility in aquaculture-related environments
2024	PolFish 2024, Gdańsk	External	Seafood sector professionals, trade audiences	Exhibition, networking	Trade and industry audience	Relevant for sector-facing visibility
2024	Conxemar 2024, Vigo	External	Seafood companies, trade professionals, associations	Trade fair dissemination, networking	Large commercial seafood audience	High relevance for seafood-sector visibility
2024	Brussels stakeholder meetings	External	Institutional, policy, and	Institutional engagement, positioning	Policy-adjacent audience	Useful for EU-level visibility and networking

			project-related actors			
Oct/24	HAICTA 2024, Samos	External	Scientific and technical communities	Scientific dissemination	Specialist conference audience	Important for technical credibility around knowledge-base development
2025	Mr. GoodFish 3.0 Co-Creation Workshop, Tromsø	External	Stakeholders, co-creation participants, seafood communication actors	Co-creation, presentation, stakeholder exchange	Focused workshop audience	Strong relevance for feedback and narrative refinement
Early 2025	European Ocean Days / Mission Ocean Forum, Brussels	External	EU policy, project clustering, sustainability and ocean actors	Policy dialogue, clustering, outreach	Institutional and project ecosystem audience	Important for strategic alignment and visibility in Mission Ocean contexts
Mar/25	AQUACULTURE 2025, New Orleans	External	International aquaculture audience, researchers, professionals	Conference dissemination	Large international professional audience	Extended visibility beyond Europe in a specialised sector environment
2025	Seafood Traceability Seminar / Sjókovin Anniversary, Faroe Islands	External	Traceability and fisheries stakeholders	Thematic discussion, networking	Focused specialist audience	Relevant to project themes of transparency and communication
2025	EuroFIR AISBL FoodForum, Brussels	External	Nutrition and food-data experts	Scientific / specialist dissemination	Expert community	Relevant for the nutrition pillar and scientific positioning
Apr/25	Seafood Expo Global 2025, Barcelona	External	Seafood industry, trade, value-chain actors	Trade fair dissemination, networking, output visibility	Large international seafood audience	One of the most relevant sector-facing events for professional visibility
2025	Market Seminar on Fisheries and Aquaculture, Vilnius	External	Fisheries and aquaculture stakeholders	Seminar, formal presentation	Targeted specialist audience	Relevant for direct presentation of framework-related content
2025	Eurofish Conference on Predators and Invasive Species, Tallinn	External	Fisheries and aquaculture professionals	Conference dissemination	Specialist conference audience	Useful for continued sector visibility
2025	A Seat at the Table – Connecting	External	Food-system and	Public discussion, awareness	Mixed stakeholder audience	Relevant for broader food

	Food, Culture, and Sustainability, Copenhagen		sustainability audiences			sustainability narrative
Sept/25	Aquaculture Europe 2025, Valencia	External	Aquaculture professionals, researchers, projects, companies	Fair participation, dissemination, networking	Large European sector audience	Important for visibility, poster dissemination, and project presence
Sept/25	Aquaculture Europe 2025 ePoster session	External	Scientific and professional conference audience	Technical presentation of the framework	Specialist audience	Relevant for communicating the framework in a conference setting
2025	14th International Food Data Conference, Rome	External	Nutrition and food-data specialists	Scientific dissemination	Specialist expert audience	Strong relevance for nutrition-related content
Oct/25	IJCKG 2025, Heraklion	External	Knowledge graph and semantic web community	Scientific dissemination	Technical specialist audience	Important for methodological and technical credibility
Nov/25	Catch Welfare Platform Conference, IJmuiden	External	Producers, associations, researchers, welfare and fisheries actors	Technical dissemination, stakeholder exchange, video content generation, working lunch validation	Highly relevant specialist audience	One of the strongest external events for feedback, validation, and content generation
Nov/25	VeriFish working lunch at Catch Welfare Platform	External / targeted engagement	Producers, associations, researchers, technology providers	App presentation, framework testing, direct feedback collection	26 selected participants	Critical event for practical validation and stakeholder input
2026	Arctic Frontiers 2026, Tromsø	External	Marine, Arctic, fisheries, and policy stakeholders	Conference outreach, traceability and responsible communication dialogue	High-level specialist audience	Strategically relevant for broader narrative positioning
2026	Market Advisory Council WG1 Meeting, Ostend	External	Market and advisory stakeholders	Presentation of app and framework, stakeholder dialogue	Focused advisory audience	One of the strongest events for direct engagement with relevant multiplier actors
2026	AquaFarm 2026, Pordenone	External	Aquaculture and seafood professionals	Trade event dissemination	Specialist sector audience	Useful for situating project tools in

						professional context
2026	Mission Ocean Forum / European Ocean Days, Brussels	External	EU policy and clustering communities	Policy dialogue, clustering, dissemination	Institutional audience	Strong relevance for strategic visibility and alignment
2026	Food 2030 Clustering Workshop, Brussels	External	Food-system and EU project actors	Clustering, dissemination	Specialist policy and project audience	Relevant for connecting VeriFish to wider food-system discussions
2026	OSCARS General Assembly, Seville	External	Open science, FAIR data, project communities	Scientific / open science visibility	Specialist audience	Relevant for technical and FAIR-data positioning
Apr/26	Seafood Expo Global 2026, Barcelona	External	Seafood trade, companies, associations, market actors	Trade fair dissemination, networking, promotion of final outputs	Large international seafood audience	Strong closing-phase sector visibility opportunity

A shorter classification by event purpose is provided below.

Table 20: VeriFish event classification by event purpose

Event purpose	Main examples	Main value for WP3
Awareness and outreach	Seafood Expo Global, Conxemar, AquaFarm, public-facing conferences	Broad professional visibility and entry points to project outputs
Scientific dissemination	HAICTA, IJCKG, IFDC, FoodForum, Aquaculture Europe poster	Technical credibility and communication to expert communities
Stakeholder engagement and validation	Catch Welfare Platform, Market Advisory Council WG1, final event validation workshop, Mr.GoodFish workshop	Two-way exchange, testing, and refinement of outputs
Policy dialogue and clustering	European Ocean Days, Mission Ocean Forum, Food 2030 workshop, Brussels stakeholder meetings	Strategic alignment, EU-level visibility, and positioning
Education and public engagement	Tromsø Seafood Festival, educational product-linked outreach	Broader accessibility and non-specialist communication pathways